

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Sweden

Country Dossier (WP2)

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Abbreviations

EU	European Union
EEA	European Economic Area
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorization System
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
NRO	National Return Operations
JRO	Joint Return Operations
NTE	National Transport Unit
CJEU	the Court of Justice of the European Union
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
ECtHR	the European Court of Human Rights
ECHR	The European Convention on Human Rights
CRC	The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child
SIS	Schengen Information System
WP	Work Package
MSs	Member States
TCN	Third-country National

Executive Summary

This report delineates the legislative, institutional, and procedural frameworks and infrastructures concerning the return of irregular migrants from Sweden. It further explores key policy developments in this field. Covering the period from 2015 to 2023, with some historical retrospectives, the report provides a brief overview of return-related statistics, elucidates the interplay between Swedish national law, EU law, and public international law, and maps the operational infrastructure for return, including the primary return governance actors at the national level. The focus is chiefly on the legislative framework, especially the transposition of the EU Return Directive into Swedish legislation, and recent legislative and policy shifts in the return context. Section 7, on the legislative framework, specifically examines return procedures, approaches to both voluntary and enforced return, procedural safeguards, detention, and the specific requirements for the return of unaccompanied minors and other vulnerable groups. Additionally, the report addresses international cooperation and funding pertaining to return.

Special emphasis is placed on the political developments in the migration sector following the so-called refugee crisis of 2015, when Sweden received a significant number of asylum seekers, and in the context of the 2022 Tidö Agreement. This agreement, a pact between the current liberal-conservative government and its coalition partner, outlines several reforms, notably in migration and integration policy areas.

A principal finding is that although (while) the EU Return Directive and later EU legislation have been incorporated into Swedish law, the Swedish government has, on numerous points, deemed such revisions unnecessary. The government has contended that existing legislation, principally the Aliens Act, already meets or surpasses the requirements of EU law, thereby obviating the need for additional measures to align Swedish law with EU directives on these matters. This includes several definitions listed in Article 3 of the Return Directive (such as ‘irregular stay’ and ‘assisted return’), and the authorised exemption from applying the Return Directive under specific conditions outlined in Articles 2.2 a) and b).

Another significant observation is that while return has long been a priority—at least on paper—in recent years, its urgency has increased. This is demonstrated by the Swedish Government’s directive to the Migration Agency to prioritise returns more than before, enhancing the efficiency of the return process and increasing the number of people actually departing Sweden. The emphasis seems to have shifted from voluntary to forced returns, which is consistent with the general trend of more stringent Swedish migration policy since 2015, which is summed up by the principle “no means no.”

This approach aims to ensure that Sweden does not deviate from the EU’s minimum standards for international protection, asylum procedures, reception conditions, and return measures. The 2022 Tidö Agreement’s reforms further cement this stringent migration stance, reflecting what has been termed a ‘paradigm shift’ in Swedish migration policy.

The report concludes by identifying gaps in the legislative, institutional, and policy frameworks (outlined in Section 9) and proposes several recommendations to the Swedish government and migration authorities, summarized as follows:

- Additional clarification of certain terms and definitions in the Aliens Act is necessary, including ‘illegal/irregular stay’, ‘assisted return’, and ‘practical impediment to return’.
- A more thorough analysis and revision of Swedish law are required to ensure compliance with EU law, particularly concerning detention and rules related to the refusal of entry or expulsion of a foreign national authorized to reside in another EU state.
- For transparency, data on returns and other migration-related issues should be aggregated and made readily accessible.
- Revisions to Swedish law in accordance with EU requirements should not primarily aim to make national legislation as restrictive as possible.
- While trying to avoid sending conflicting messages to migrants by aiming for "no to mean no," efforts must be made to safeguard fundamental rights and incorporate safety-valve provisions for new circumstances.
- Provisional measures should accompany stricter restrictions on granting residence permits, with proper evaluation of their proportionality and long-term impacts.
- Fundamental human rights standards and the principle of proportionality must always be upheld—the state’s interest in pursuing a restrictive migration policy should not override all other considerations.

Keywords: return policy – migration governance –Sweden – Swedish return policy – Swedish migration law – Return Directive

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

This report aims to provide an overview of Sweden's legal, institutional and policy framework on returns and readmission. It also covers cooperation between Sweden and the European Union (EU) in this field as well as bilateral cooperation between Sweden and other Member States and third countries. The report aims to identify gaps in the legal, institutional and policy frameworks described and, on this basis, provide some brief policy recommendations.

2. Methodology and Material

The report adheres to guidelines jointly developed by the participating researchers in GAPs WP 2. Building on a shared template allows comparative analysis across all participating countries.

Section 1 introduces the aims of the report and **Section 2** outlines the methodology and materials used. **Section 3** provides an overview of statistical data on returns from Sweden. The majority of the statistical data included in this report was obtained through correspondence with the Swedish Migration Agency and Swedish Police Authority, supplemented by data sourced from their websites and from the Eurostat database. While much of the information is available on the Migration Agency and Police Authority websites, the statistical data used in this report has been consolidated into a unified dataset by the Swedish Migration Agency. **Section 4** gives a brief overview of key developments in Swedish migration and protection policy, with a particular focus on matters related to return. **Section 5** briefly outlines the relationship between Swedish law, public international law, and EU law. In **Section 6**, the institutional framework and operational infrastructure for returns is outlined. Sections 4, 5 and 6 relies on legislative materials, preparatory works, case law, secondary literature and information sourced from the Police Authority website and the Migration Agency Handbook. **Section 7**, which aims to provide an account of the Swedish legal framework on return and its relationship with EU law, is based on desk research on the Swedish Aliens Act and other related Swedish legislation on migration, EU law, and the preparatory works of such regulations. These preparatory works include official reports from government inquiries and government bills reflecting the processes of current and previous successive governments leading to the implementation of EU law in national legislation, particularly the Return Directive. **Section 8** discusses the funding of return-related programs, using information from the Migration Agency's website, targeting returnees and others. In the final Section, **Section 9**, we describe the main gaps in the legal and institutional framework identified in the report and make recommendations based on the findings presented. A draft version of the findings was discussed with an expert panel in December 2023 before the finalization of the report. The report has been subject to external review.

3. Statistical Overview

The charts on the following page provide a statistical overview of return and return-related matters in Sweden from 2015 to September 2023. The charts are as follows: **Chart 1.** the number of asylum seeker applications; **Chart 2.** the number of Dublin return cases; **Chart 3.** the number of return decisions resulting from denied asylum applications by the Migration Agency; **Chart 4.** the number of assisted voluntary return cases, **Chart 5.** the number of assisted forced return cases, and **Chart 6.** the number of non-assisted voluntary return cases.

While collecting statistical data for the report, we communicated extensively with the Migration Agency and the Police Authority. The charts are based on information from these two government agencies.¹ The two government agencies' responses to specific questions about statistical data collection procedures in the context of the return process can be summarized as follows:

The Police Authority:

Regarding the stock of irregular migrants in Sweden: The Police Authority states that it is not possible to provide any accurate assessment of the number of irregular migrants present in Swedish territory. The Police Authority, however, still has data on open cases involving individuals without the necessary permits to stay in Sweden and have enforceable decisions against them. This data does not represent a complete count due to various situations, such as cases that have expired without applying for new permits, aliens who entered Sweden irregularly and who have not regularized their status, and many more.

Regarding the number of rejections of entry at the border for third-country foreign nationals: The Police Authority referred to figures available on their website, indicating "polisavvisningar vid yttre gräns," which relates to rejections at the entry to Sweden from non-European Union (EU)/European Economic Area (EEA) countries. These individuals are typically put on return flights. According to the Police Authority, the internal border controls in other Schengen countries consist of random checks only. The statistics reflect the number of rejections at these internal border controls and do not represent the total number of third-country nationals (TCNs) who would be rejected if inspected. Denied entry usually leads to a refusal-of-entry decision.

Regarding the number of pushback cases for TCNs with no right to enter Sweden: The term "pushback" is not used in Swedish law. The Police Authority rejects the suggestion that illegal pushbacks are conducted at the Swedish border or within Swedish jurisdiction. (While it is impossible to say with absolute certainty, it should be noted that there are few, if any, reports of illegal pushbacks at Swedish borders.) Foreign citizens who are not eligible for entry will, according to the Police Authority, be denied entry and returned to their country of origin or last departure point.

¹ It may be noted that Eurostat data and the data from the Swedish Migration Agency sometimes are not identical. For more information see Eurostat, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/EN/migr_eil_esqrs_se.htm (accessed March 18, 2024).

The Swedish Migration Agency:

On whether existing data on returns and readmissions are disaggregated: The Migration Agency responded that the data is not disaggregated.

The Swedish Migration Agency is the sole authority responsible for collecting this data. Other authorities, such as the Police Authority, are not involved in this process. As per the Swedish Migration Agency's response, the data is not generally collected in a systematic and coherent way.

4. The Political Context of the Swedish Return Regime

4.1 Introduction

Sweden can generally be characterized as a liberal democracy with a centralized state that, as Malm Lindberg notes, 'generally has a high capacity in implementing policies in different fields'.² To understand the Swedish system, it is essential to note that Swedish government agencies, including the Migration Agency and the Police Authority, are independent and largely autonomous in relation to the government. Although the government can influence how government agencies operate through annual monitoring and evaluations, top-level management appointments, and annual appropriation directives and ordinances, it is not able to interfere with an agency's decision-making regarding the proper application of the law or the appropriate use of its authority.³ Ministerial rule is in other words not allowed in Sweden.

² Henrik Malm Lindberg, "The Tricky Thing of Implementing Migration Policies: Insights from Return Policies in Sweden" in *Migration and Integration in a Post-Pandemic World. Socioeconomic Opportunities and Challenges*, ed. Lin Leopold, Örjan Sjöberg and Karl Wennberg (Springer, 2023), 151-175 (158).

³ For an overview of how Swedish public agencies are governed, see <https://www.government.se/how-sweden-is-governed/public-agencies-and-how-they-are-governed/> (last accessed January 3, 2024).

Timeline of the Return Policy in Sweden

2015 - 2023

4.2 1999-2014: Gradually Increasing Focus on Return

From 1999 to the present, Sweden, known for its extensive welfare state and dedication to social equality, has seen notable changes in its migration policy.⁴

In 1999, the Migration Agency was given primary responsibility for the enforcement of return decisions as well as for persons in detention. Previously, it had mainly been the Police Authority, which had been tasked with the enforcement of returns. This responsibility was now limited to specific categories of return.⁵ The aim of the return policy at the turn of the millennium was for the majority of returns to be voluntary and for the number of forced

⁴ See e.g., Elisabeth Abiri, "The Changing Praxis of 'Generosity': Swedish Refugee Policy during the 1990s," *Journal of Refugee Studies*, Vol. 13, No. 1, March (2000): 11–28; Karin Borevi, "Family Migration Policies and Politics: Understanding the Swedish Exception," *Journal of Family Issues*, Vol. 36, Issue 11, (2015): 1490-1508; Klara Öberg and Maja Sager, "Articulations of Deportability: Changing Migration Policies in Sweden 2015/2016," *Refugee Review*, Vol. 3 (2017): 2-14; Rebecca Thorburn Stern, "Proportionate or Panicky?: On Developments in Swedish and Nordic Asylum Law in Light Of the 2015 'Refugee Crisis,'" in *The New Asylum and Transit Countries in Europe During and in the Aftermath of the 2015/2016 Crisis*, ed. Eleni Karageorgiou and Vladislava Stoyanova (Brill Academic Publishers, 2018), 233-262; Malm Lindberg (2023), "The Tricky Thing of Implementing Migration Policies"; Christine M. Jacobsen, Marry-Anne Karlsen, Shahram Khosravi, eds. *Waiting and the Temporalities of Irregular Migration* (Routledge, 2020); Anna Lundberg, "Pushed Out in Limbo – The Every-day Decision-Making about 'Practical Impediments to Enforcement' in the Swedish Management of Return Migration," *Retfærd. Nordisk Juridisk Tidsskrift*, Vol. 3, No. 3, (2020): 13-31.

⁵ See Section 5 of this report.

returns to decrease.⁶ During the early 2000s, the necessity of enforcing return decisions, however, was increasingly emphasised in several Migration Agency appropriation directions.⁷ In 2006, the current Aliens Act⁸ entered into force. Following the September 2006 general elections, a new centre-right coalition came into power in Sweden. During its term of office, migration policies increasingly focused on return efforts rather than reception activities, including enforcement.⁹ An exception, however, was labour migration from third (non-EU) countries, the regulation of which was liberalised in 2008.¹⁰ Around 2010, ambitions regarding return were raised.¹¹ One example is the REVA project ("Rättssäkert och Effektivt Verkställighetsarbete", meaning 'Legally Secure and Efficient Enforcement'). REVA was a government-initiated project operating between 2011 and 2014 that sought to boost the effectiveness of enforcement of deportations of persons staying in Sweden on a long-term basis without possessing the permits necessary for doing so. REVA was a joint operation between the Police Authority, the Prison and Probation Service and the Migration Agency. The project was much debated as it raised concerns about racial profiling, in particular regarding the parts of the project involving the Police Authority.¹²

4.3 2015-2021: The Migration 'Crisis' and its Aftermath

In 2014, a Social Democrat-Green coalition won the general elections. The new government, however, did not lead to any substantial changes to the migration policy.¹³ During the 2015 'migration crisis', Sweden received over 160,000 asylum seekers in a few months.¹⁴ While initially welcoming, public opinion as well as the political debate gradually began to shift towards a more hostile stance. The watershed moment was in November 2015 when temporary border controls and a new restrictive asylum policy were introduced, the aim being to provide Sweden with 'breathing space'.¹⁵ The new policy has been described as a paradigm shift in Swedish migration policy.¹⁶ The new policy was codified mainly through the 2016 so-called "Temporary Law",¹⁷ which was revised in 2019 and ceased to apply in July 2021. The key feature of the Temporary Law, which was to be applied instead of the Aliens Act in cases of overlapping norms, was that it introduced temporary residence permits for refugees and

⁶ Prop. (Government Bill) *Verkställighet och återvändande – en del av asylprocessen*, 1997/98:173.

⁷ Henrik Malm Lindberg, *Delmi rapport 2020:1 De som inte får stanna. Att implementera återvändandepolitik*, 24.

⁸ Swedish Parliament. *Aliens Act*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2005:716.

⁹ Malm Lindberg, "The Tricky Thing of Implementing Migration Policies," 159.

¹⁰ See Catharina Calleman and Petra Herzfeld Olsson, eds., *Arbetskraft från hela världen: Hur blev det med 2008 års reform? Delmi report 2015:9*.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² See e.g. Stina Fredrika Wassen, "Where Does Securitisation Begin? The Institutionalised Securitisation of Illegal Immigration in Sweden: REVA and the ICFs," *Contemporary Voices: St Andrews Journal of International Relations*, Vol. 1, Issue 1 (2018): 78-103.

¹³ Cf. Jonas Hinnfors, Andrea Spehar and Gregg Bucken-Knapp, "The Missing Factor: Why Social Democracy Can Lead to Restrictive Immigration Policy," *Journal of European Public Policy* Vol.19 Issue 4, (2012): 585–603.

¹⁴ SOU (Swedish Government Official Reports), *Att ta emot människor på flykt. Sverige hösten 2015*, 2017:12.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ Thorburn Stern, "Proportionate or Panicky? On Developments in Swedish and Nordic Asylum Law in Light Of the 2015 'Refugee Crisis'."

¹⁷ Swedish Parliament, *Om tillfälliga begränsningar av möjligheten att få uppehållstillstånd i Sverige (The Temporary Law)*, Svensk Författningssamling (SFS) 2016:752.

grantees of subsidiary protection status as the new main rule (previously, these categories have been granted permanent residence permits from the beginning), reduced the number of grounds for a residence permit compared to the Aliens Act, including humanitarian grounds, and introduced more restrictive rules on family reunification.¹⁸

Another temporary legislation introduced post-2015 was the so-called Upper Secondary School Act ("Gymnasielagen"). In short, the legislation allowed for young people (under the age of 25) who had been granted a temporary residence permit based on the 2016 Temporary Law for studies on the upper secondary school level to be granted a temporary residence permit for the duration of their studies and an additional six months. Such permits, moreover, under certain circumstances, could be prolonged, for example, to find work or form the basis for a permanent residence permit. The first version of the law (formally part of the Temporary Law) applied until July 2021. When the Temporary Law expired, a new, revised version of the Upper Secondary School Act entered into force.¹⁹ The possibility of being granted a residence permit for upper secondary school-level studies ceased to apply in December 2023. The possibility of prolonging residence permits based on the law or turning them into permanent residence permits will cease to apply in 2024 and 2025.

The government took several initiatives during the 2015-2021 phase to increase the number of returns. Examples include instructing the Migration Agency to work more effectively with returns (voluntary and enforced), including increased and more effective cooperation with The Police Authority and the Prison and Probation Service.²⁰ On the policy and legislative level, several Government Commissions of Inquiry²¹ were initiated addressing issues of relevance for return, some also leading to legislative changes. One of these was the 2017 Government Commission on Return, whose proposals included extended possibilities for The Police Authority to use intrusive measures when carrying out internal border control. The proposals became part of the Aliens Act in 2021 and 2023, respectively.

In 2019, the government appointed an all-party Commission of Inquiry to establish a long-term, sustainable migration policy. It may be noted that return policy was not among the key points on the Commission's agenda. In the spring of 2020, the Swedish National Audit Office presented a report evaluating the implementation of the return policy in the years 2013-2018, pointing to several gaps in the implementation, including a lack of cooperation between government authorities, increasing costs, lack of fulfilment of policy goals, lack of overall perspective and conflicting goals between the requirements of the return operations and other regulations and conditions that partially serve other purposes.²² The report concluded that the

¹⁸ For an overview, see e.g. Prop. (Government Bill) *Tillfälliga begränsningar av möjligheten att få uppehållstillstånd i Sverige* 2015/16:174, and Prop. (Government Bill) *Förlängning av lagen om tillfälliga begränsningar av möjligheten att få uppehållstillstånd i Sverige*, 2018/19:128.

¹⁹ Swedish Parliament, *Om uppehållstillstånd för studerande på gymnasial nivå, (Upper Secondary School Act)*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2017: 353.

²⁰ Malm Lindberg, "The Tricky Thing of Implementing Migration Policies."

²¹ Government commissions of inquiry (and, occasionally, all-party commissions of inquiry) play an important role in the Swedish legislative process. The report of the inquiry and the thereupon following comments from the consultation bodies provide the basis for the government bill to be presented to the Riksdag. For an overview of the Swedish legislative process see e.g. <https://www.government.se/contentassets/4490fe7afcbo40b0822840fa460dd858/the-swedish-law-making-process/> (last accessed December 3, 2023) and Christoffer Wong and Michael Bogdan, eds. *Swedish Legal System*, 2nd ed. (Stockholm, Norstedts Juridik, 2022).

²² Swedish National Audit Office, *Återvändandeverksamheten – resultat, kostnader och effektivitet*, RIR 2020:7.

goals of the return policy, decided by the Riksdag and the government, to a large extent were not satisfactory fulfilled. In September 2020, the all-party Commission of Inquiry presented its report on the future migration policy. Many of its recommendations aimed to make most of the provisions of the Temporary Law permanent.²³ It is interesting to note that although return for years had been a prioritised matter, at least on paper, return policy was only mentioned in passing in the Inquiry's report, in the analysis of the consequences of the proposals

Due to political differences, the all-party Commission of Inquiry did not reach a consensus on several issues, such as humanitarian grounds for residence permits. Later in 2020, the government, as part of an agreement with the Green Party, presented an additional proposal for a revised humanitarian ground, extending the scope of the existing Aliens Act humanitarian ground.²⁴ The proposals were all turned into a Government Bill which, in June 2021, the Riksdag after heated debate adopted as amendments and changes to the 2006 Aliens Act.²⁵

4.4 2022-Present: A New Era?

In June 2022 the government initiated a new Commission on Inquiry focusing on return, aimed at analysing how returns could be made more effective and increasing the possibility of using control measures on aliens in the return process.²⁶ The Inquiry's tasks were extended in August 2023, the official report to be presented in 2024.²⁷ Simultaneously, the government tasked the Migration Agency with analysing the introduction of 'return centres', that is specialised accommodations for individuals who have received an enforceable decision of transfer, deportation, or expulsion.

In September 2022, general elections were held. The election campaign substantially focused on migration and integration, particularly its perceived negative aspects. A centre-right coalition, with the support of the right-wing populist party, the Sweden Democrats, gained the majority. The coalition and its support party – without the support of which the coalition could not have formed a government – in late 2022 presented a comprehensive reform agenda known as the Tidö Agreement, a large part of which is dedicated to migration and immigration.²⁸ Return is mentioned explicitly in the Tidö Agreement as a prioritised field, including increasing the use of detention and other restrictions of the freedom of movement to enforce return decisions.²⁹ The overall focus of the Tidö reforms can be summarised as to

²³ See the Official Report of the Inquiry: *En långsiktigt hållbar migrationspolitik*, SOU 2020:54.

²⁴ Prop. (Government Bill), *Ändrade regler i utlänningslagen*, 2020/21:191.

²⁵ *Ändrade regler i utlänningslagen*, 2020/21: SfU28.

²⁶ Dir. (Terms of Reference) 2022:91 *Åtgärder för att stärka återvändandeverksamheten*. On the function of Commissions of Inquiry in the Swedish legislative process, please see e.g. <https://www.government.se/contentassets/4490fe7afc040b0822840fa460dd858/the-swedish-law-making-process/> (last accessed December 13, 2023) and Christoffer Wong and Michael Bogdan, eds., *Swedish Legal System* (Norstedts Juridik, 2022).

²⁷ Dir. (Terms of Reference) 2023:126 *Tilläggsdirektiv till Utredningen om stärkt återvändandeverksamhet* (Ju 2022:12).

²⁸ The Conservative Party/The Liberal Party/The Christian Democrats/The Sweden Democrats, "The Tidö Agreement," 2022, <https://via.tt.se/data/attachments/00551/04f31218-dccc-4e58-a129-09952cae07e7.pdf> (last accessed Januari 2, 2024).

²⁹ *Tidö Agreement* (2022), 33.

make Sweden less accessible as well as less attractive for migrants, asylum seekers in particular, with several detailed suggestions on how this is to be realised. It may be noted that the Tidö Agreement explicitly states that asylum seekers' rights should be limited as much as possible.

Sweden held the Presidency of the Council of the European Union in the first half of 2023. One of the main aims of the Presidency was to bring the work on the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum forward. Also, in 2023, the new government launched several commissions of inquiry to analyse the reforms outlined in the Tidö Agreement and produce proposals for legislative changes to realise the reforms. These commissions of inquiry are, for example, tasked with analysing and proposing new rules on detention³⁰, on cessation and revocation of residence permits,³¹ and on streamlining Swedish asylum law with the minimum standards required by EU asylum law.³² The government aims for the majority of the Tidö reforms to have been made into "hard law" before the general elections scheduled for September 2026. An example of the reforms already put in place at the time of writing is the creation of 'return centres', which the Migration Agency was tasked with in June 2023. The first five centres became operational in October 2023 (accommodating approx. 650 persons).³³ It is not obligatory for a person with an enforceable return decision to relocate to one of the centres, but not doing so may have adverse effects on the right to accommodation in Migration Agency housing.³⁴

5. The Institutional Framework/Operational Infrastructure: Return Governance Actors

Multiple actors play critical roles in Sweden's return governance. This section summarizes the roles of the Migration Agency and the Police Authority, along with descriptions of other actors, their institutional frameworks, and operational infrastructure.

As already mentioned, the Migration Agency, since 1999, holds the primary responsibility for decisions on return, the enforcement of return decisions, and detention. A rejection of an application for a residence permit is usually accompanied by a refusal-of-entry or expulsion order (Aliens Act, Chapter 8, Section 16). When the order has taken legal effect, it is to be enforced, provided there are no impediments to enforcement (see Section 7.2.2 below).³⁵ The persons to whom the refusal-of-entry or expulsion order applies are expected to return on a voluntary basis, if needed with the support of the Swedish Migration Agency.

³⁰ Dir. (Terms of Reference) 2023:119, *Moderna och ändamålsenliga regler för förvar*.

³¹ Dir. (Terms of Reference) 2023:158, *Skärpta krav på hederligt levnadssätt och ökade möjligheter till återkallelse av uppehållstillstånd*.

³² Dir. (Terms of Reference) 2023:137, *Anpassning av det svenska regelverket för beviljande av asyl och asylförfarandet till miniminivån enligt EU-rätten*.

³³ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Pressrum/Nyhetsarkiv/Nyhetsarkiv-2023/2023-10-17-Migrationsverket-startar-atervandandecenter.html> (last accessed December 18, 2023).

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Certain return decisions may however be enforced before they have taken legal effect, such as when it stands clear that an asylum application is obviously unfounded (*Aliens Act*, Chapter 8, Section 19 and Chapter 12, Section 7).

Once there is a refusal-of-entry or expulsion order (or when the alien has withdrawn his/her asylum application), the Migration Agency initiates what is referred to as “the return process”. This process thus starts even before the decision has taken legal effect. The process aims to support individuals who do not possess the necessary permits to remain in Sweden to return voluntarily. The different steps of the return process (routines, etc.) are described in detail in the Migration Agency Handbook on Return,³⁶ an internal Migration Agency document. These steps include the measures to be taken to notify the alien of the decision on rejection of the application for a residence permit, routines for so-called “return information meetings” (“återvändandesamtal”), routines for providing information about Migration Agency return centres (to which failed applicants in Migration Agency housing are to transfer at the latest when the refusal-of-entry or expulsion order has taken legal effect)³⁷, categorization of cases depending on the feasibility of carrying out the refusal-of-entry or expulsion order (“verkställbarhetskategorisering”)³⁸ routines on providing information about financial support upon return and for transferring a case to the Police Authority. The return process at the Migration Agency ends once the alien leaves Sweden, the case is transferred to the Police Authority or when the decision is subject to statutory limitation.

The Migration Agency maintains the responsibility for enforcing the refusal-of-entry or expulsion order (Aliens Act Chapter 12, Section 14, Subsection 1) except when *i*) the case falls within the responsibility of the Swedish Security Service or *ii*) it is the responsibility of the Police Authority (see Section 7.3 below). The Migration Agency may transfer an expulsion or deportation case for enforcement to the Police Authority if the person to be expelled or deported is evading the authorities and cannot be found without the assistance of the Police Authority or if it can be assumed that force will be needed to enforce the decision (Aliens Act Chapter 12 Section 14 Subsection 4).

Deportation and expulsion cases differ regarding coercion between the Police Authority and the Migration Agency. Cases involving police enforcement entail coercion, whereas those managed by the Migration Agency are typically voluntary.

The Police Authority is mandated to apprehend aliens without a legal right to stay in Sweden or when tasked with enforcing return decisions, as long as the return decision remains valid. In cases of unsuccessful enforcement, the Police Authority reports back to the Migration Agency for case reviewing. The statute of limitations lasts four years after the decision becomes legally binding. The Prison and Probation Service plays a role in planning, booking, and executing enforced return journeys on behalf of the police, underscoring the Police Authority’s continued responsibility.

However, the Migration Agency manages detention centres where individuals await enforcement of their return decisions (see Section 7.9 of the report for further information). In Sweden, return enforcement operations fall into National Return Operations (NRO) and Joint Return Operations (JRO). The critical distinction between them is that JROs involve collaborative efforts between two or more EU states who share a chartered flight to carry out

³⁶ Migration Agency, “Handbook on Return” (Handbok för processområde Asyl – Återvändandeprocessen) version 1.0, (last accessed October 18, 2023).

³⁷ Individuals living in private housing are not forced to move to the return centres, but are offered the possibility.

³⁸ This could for example include identifying whether the alien in question is positive towards returning voluntarily.

return enforcement. This collaboration is often driven by cost-effectiveness and security considerations. Frontex substantially covers the costs of JROs, whereas NROs receive partial coverage. It is up to the Swedish authorities to initiate Frontex's involvement. On return journeys, accompanying personnel include members from the Swedish Prison and Probation Service's National Transport Unit (NTE) and The Police Authority. An interpreter, medical staff, and an independent monitor who reports to Frontex and the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights are also part of the operation. According to 2019 statistics, the Police Authority executes approximately two-thirds of return decisions voluntarily, while one-third requires escort personnel.³⁹ Most trips are conducted via regular flights, with some involving chartered flights. In 2017, there were 28 joint return operations in which Sweden acted as an organizer or participant. This number was 30 in 2016 and 29 in 2015.

Table 1: Return Governance Actors

Authority	Tier of government (national, regional, local)	Type of organization	Area of competence in the fields of return (Briefly explain the role)	Link
The Migration Agency (Migrationsverket)	National	Government agency	Voluntary return	https://shorturl.at/hvADM
The Police Authority (Polisen)	National	Government agency	Execution of expulsion and deportation decision with coercion	https://shorturl.at/ktJU2
The Prison and Probation Service (Kriminalvården)	National	Government agency	Execution of expulsion and deportation decision with coercion	N/A
The Security Service	National	Government agency	Return in security cases	https://shorturl.at/jrGI0

³⁹ The Police Authority, "Frågor och svar om verkställighet." Polisen, <https://polisen.se/om-polisen/polisens-arbete/granspolisen/fragor-och-svar-om-verkstallighet/> (accessed October 25, 2023).

6. On the Relationship between Swedish Law, EU Law and Public International Law

6.1 Implementing Public International Law in Sweden

Sweden is customarily perceived as a country in the dualist tradition, that is, one in which international law and national law are considered to be two different legal systems.⁴⁰ In a dualist country, international law must be “translated” into national law to be directly applicable nationally. The methods for implementing public international law into the Swedish legal system vary depending on whether the rule in question is a rule of customary international law or a treaty ratified by Sweden. In the former case, implementation is usually handled through rules of interpretation or presumption rules. In the case of treaties, one often used method is *the affirmation of normative harmony*, which refers to when the Riksdag, concurrent with ratifying a treaty, determines that Sweden satisfies all treaty obligations without necessitating amendments or supplements to national legislation.⁴¹ A second approach is *transformation*, which in the Swedish legal context refers to rewriting and integrating treaty text, or portions thereof, into existing legislation. Transformation is the predominant method for integrating public international law into Swedish jurisprudence.⁴² A third method is *incorporation*, which in Swedish legal tradition refers to when the entire treaty or its pivotal Sections are directly rendered into Swedish law through a specific act of legislation.⁴³ In addition to these methods, the *principle of consistent interpretation* also applies in Swedish law.⁴⁴

Sweden has ratified most of the core UN human rights treaties (see Table 4), as well as the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol. The preferred method for implementation in these cases has been transformation. As a result, the treaties cannot be directly invoked in Swedish courts. Nevertheless, all treaties ratified by Sweden, given the principle of consistent interpretation, must be considered when interpreting Swedish law. Conflicts between international and national law are usually avoided by applying the abovementioned principle.⁴⁵

Of treaties particularly relevant in the field of asylum and migration law, only the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) at the time of writing have been fully incorporated into Swedish law, thus forming part of its statutory corpus. The ECHR enjoys distinct constitutional protection within Swedish law. Chapter 2, Section 19 of the Instrument of Government (one of four fundamental laws forming the Swedish Constitution) states that no law or other provision conflicting with

⁴⁰ Ove Bring, Mark Klamberg, Said Mahmoudi and Pål Wrangé, *Sverige och folkrätten* 6 ed., (Norstedts Juridik, 2020); David Thór Bjorgvinsson, *The Intersection of International Law and Domestic Law: A Theoretical and Practical Analysis* (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2015); Carl-Henrik Ehrenkrona, “Sveriges internationella avtal och dessas genomförande i svensk lagstiftning – några reflektioner,” *Svensk Juristtidning* (2015): 779.

⁴¹ Ehrenkrona, “Sveriges internationella avtal,” 779.

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ *ibid.*

⁴⁵ See e.g. Maria Grahn Farley, “Fördragskonform tolkning av MR-traktat,” *Svensk Juristtidning*, No. 5 (2018): 450–463.

Sweden's obligations under the ECHR may be enacted. The CRC, however, does not hold the same status in Swedish law as the ECHR; it instead enjoys the same place in the legal hierarchy as "ordinary law."

Judgments of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) are, as follows by ECHR Article 46, binding on the state in any case in which it is a party. Since the incorporation of the ECHR, the treaty, as well as ECtHR jurisprudence, have progressively exerted a notable influence over the interpretation and application of Swedish law, including migration law.⁴⁶ The Swedish Migration Agency and the migration courts regularly reference ECtHR jurisprudence.⁴⁷ Over the years, several cases of migration-related issues against Sweden have been addressed by the ECtHR and, in certain instances, have led to significant alterations or clarifications in Swedish practice, one example being the much-cited *RC v. Sweden* (2010) on the allocation of the burden of proof.⁴⁸

On the other hand, jurisprudence by monitoring bodies of UN human rights treaties such as the CRC Committee, the Human Rights Committee, and the Committee on Torture is not considered legally binding on Sweden. Such jurisprudence is nevertheless considered to provide authoritative interpretations of the treaties and is, at least to some extent, referred to in case law and preparatory works.⁴⁹ Moreover, the Aliens Act, Chapter 5, Section 4, stipulates that if an international body such as the Human Rights Committee finds that enforcing an expulsion order would be contrary to a Swedish commitment under a convention, a residence permit shall be granted to the person covered by the order, unless there are exceptional grounds against granting a residence permit. In an early judgment, MIG 2006:1, the Migration Court of Appeal declared the UNHCR Handbook to be considered a source of law in Sweden, thus indicating its relatively strong position in Swedish jurisprudence.

6.2 Implementing EU law in Sweden

Following a 1994 referendum, Sweden officially became an EU member state in 1995 after signing an accession agreement in June 1994. The 1994 Act of Accession governs Sweden's membership in the EU. The Instrument of Government, Chapter 10, Section 6, stipulates that the Riksdag may transfer decision-making authority within the framework of the EU corporation, provided it does not affect the fundamental principles by which Sweden is governed. Such transfer presupposes that protection for rights and freedoms in the field of cooperation to which the transfer relates corresponds to that afforded under the Instrument of Government and the ECHR. The Riksdag may decide to transfer decision-making powers if at least three-quarters of the members vote and more than half of the members of the Riksdag support the decision. Sweden's status as an EU member state is explicitly stated in the Instrument of Government Chapter 1, Section 10.

The cardinal principle of the primacy of EU law dictates that in a conflict between EU law and national law, EU law takes precedence. This principle has evolved through the

⁴⁶ Rebecca Thorburn Stern, "Folkrätten i svensk migrationsrätt," in *Folkrätten i svensk rätt: Ett nytt decennium*, ed. Anna-Sara Lind, Rebecca Thorburn Stern and Inger Österdahl (Lund: Studentlitteratur 2024, *forthcoming*).

⁴⁷ See e.g. the Migration Court of Appeal judgments MIG 2008:42, MIG 2015:17 and MIG 2018:20.

⁴⁸ European Court of Human Rights, *R.C. v. Sweden*, Appl. No. 41827/07, June 9, 2010.

⁴⁹ Thorburn Stern (2024), *forthcoming*.

jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) and has been embraced by member states, Sweden included. There is no specific provision in the Swedish Instrument of Government that directly addresses the primacy of EU law.

In Sweden, this implementation of EU law predominantly transpires through adopting new legislation by the Riksdag or the amendment or revision of existing legislation. The latter method has been predominant in migration and asylum law. Legislative acts such as the Qualification Directive (recast)⁵⁰, the Asylum Procedures Directive (recast)⁵¹, the Reception Conditions Directive (recast)⁵² and the Return Directive⁵³ have thus been incorporated into the Swedish Aliens Act. In several cases, such as the Reception Conditions Directive (recast), no actual changes or amendments were, however, considered necessary as the Aliens Act was found already to fulfil the requirements of the Directive. In the case of the Return Directive and the Reception Conditions Directive (recast), there have been discussions as to whether the EU provisions on detention have been sufficiently implemented into Swedish law.⁵⁴ In recent case law, such as MIG 2020:14 and MIG 2021:3, the Migration Court of Appeal has pointed to possible discrepancies between the EU directives and the Swedish Aliens Act and emphasized the importance of upholding the primacy of EU law.

The CJEU's judgments hold pivotal significance for the interpretation of EU law and are binding on Swedish courts when applying EU law. Although there is no explicit provision in the Instrument of Government addressing the CJEU's judgments, Sweden, by its EU membership, is committed to adhering to the EU's legal order, which encompasses the CJEU's case law.

Swedish courts of the last instance have the option, and under certain circumstances the obligation, to request a preliminary ruling from the CJEU.⁵⁵ It may be noted that, despite Sweden having been a member of the EU for nearly 30 years at the time of writing, the number of requests for preliminary rulings, including in the field of asylum and migration law, remains limited.

⁵⁰ Dir. 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (recast) OJ L 337, 20.12.2011, 9–26.

⁵¹ Dir. 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (recast) OJ L 180, 29.6.2013, 60–95.

⁵² Dir. 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast), OJ L 180, 29.6.2013, 96–116.

⁵³ Dir. 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals, OJ L 348, 24.12.2008. 98–107.

⁵⁴ Simon Andersson, "Förvar och principerna för tvång," *Juridisk Tidskrift*, No. 2 (2020): 367–405.

⁵⁵ Cf. the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), Article 267, and judgments by the Swedish Supreme Court: NJA 2009:66 and NJA 2022:86.

7. The Swedish Legal Framework on Return

7.1 Introduction

The key legal instrument in Swedish migration law, including regarding matters of return, is the 2006 Aliens Act. The Aliens Act is supplemented by the 2006 Aliens Ordinance⁵⁶ and several additional Acts and Ordinances (see Table 7) including the Administrative Act and the Administrative Procedures Act, as well as by EU law and international treaties and customary law in human rights and refugee law.

This Section aims to provide an overview of the Swedish legal framework that governs multiple facets of the return regime. Key objectives include outlining the procedures for issuing deportation and expulsion orders, addressing instances of refusal or return at the border, internal and exit checks, control mechanisms, voluntary departure, re-entry bans, the return of unaccompanied minors, Dublin cases, procedural safeguards within this context, including the principle of non-refoulement, and fundamental conditions related to return detention. Furthermore, we delve into unique cases within the realm of return. The overview also describes the measures undertaken by the Swedish government to implement relevant EU legislation, primarily focusing on the 2008 Return Directive. The EMN considered the Return Directive to be fully implemented into Swedish law in 2017.⁵⁷

7.2 Return-related Definitions in Swedish Law

Several terms and definitions in the Return Directive or the Return Regulation⁵⁸ have not been transformed into the Swedish Aliens Act or other Swedish legislation. Such terms and definitions include third-country nationals, illegal/irregular stay, return, return decision, removal order, risk of absconding, voluntary departure/return, assisted return, and vulnerable persons. In the government bill on the implementation of the EU Return Directive, the government explained this approach by stating that the existing legal framework already aligned with the Directive's requirements on this point, thus making it unnecessary to introduce specific definitions into the Aliens Act (as will be detailed in the following Sections).⁵⁹ It can be added that while the Aliens Act indeed includes a chapter on definitions (Aliens Act Chapter 1 on "The content of the law, certain definitions, and general provisions"), many of its key concepts remain undefined.

Notably, the government held that it was unnecessary to establish a definition for *illegal stay* despite the absence of a Swedish legal provision explicitly outlining what constitutes illegal stay. The government's reason is that "illegal stay" is indirectly defined through the definition of "legal stay" provided by the Aliens Act (that is, if it is not legal, it is illegal).⁶⁰

⁵⁶ Swedish Parliament. *Utlänningsförordning*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2006:97.

⁵⁷ European Migration Network (EMN)/Migrationsverket, *EMN Focussed Study 2017. The Effectiveness of Return in EU Member States: Challenges and Good Practices Linked to EU Rules and Standards – Country Report Sweden*. EMN 2017.

⁵⁸ Regulation (EU) 2018/1860 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 November 2018 on the use of the Schengen Information System for the return of illegally staying third-country nationals.

⁵⁹ Prop. (Government Bill) *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*. 2011/12:60, 7.

⁶⁰ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 26.

Regarding the definitions of *return* and *removal*, a similar line of reasoning was presented in the government bill.⁶¹ On this point, the government held that this requirement had already been met due to the presence of two forms of removal – rejection, expulsion and/or deportation – within the Aliens Act.⁶² The Aliens Act outlines, rather than defines, the grounds that may constitute a basis for *refusal* and *rejection* decisions (“*avvisning*”) in Chapter 8 Sections 2-5, as well as for *removal*, *expulsion*, and *deportation* decisions (“*utvisning*”) in Chapter 8, Section 6. The Aliens Act Chapter 8a specifies the grounds for removal, expulsion, and deportation (*utvisning*) based on suspected criminality, taking into account the provisions of the Terrorism Offenses Act (2022:666)⁶³ and the Act (2022:700) on the Special Control of Certain Foreigners.⁶⁴ Thus, the Aliens Act Chapters 8 – 8a distinguishes, without providing explicit definitions, between the grounds for removal, expulsion and deportation respectively due to non-criminal and criminal activities.

Swedish law also lacks a definition of *third-country national* (TCN). The legislative amendments introduced in the context of implementing the EU Return Directive and its follow-up did not incorporate such a definition. Instead, the Aliens Act, Chapter 1, provides definitions of an EU Member State, EEA countries and EEA citizens, Schengen member states, Schengen visa, and Schengen convention and the Free Movement Directive⁶⁵.

There is also no definition in Swedish law of "*rejection, refusal, removal, expulsion or deportation decision*". The legislative amendments introduced in the context of implementing the Return Directive and its follow-up did not incorporate such a definition. Instead, the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 17, Chapter 8 a, Section 10 and Chapter 12, Section 14) and the Act (2022:700) Concerning Special Control of Certain Aliens determine the grounds on which such decisions may be issued, the authorities mandated to issue them, how they may be appealed (the Aliens Act, Chapter 14) and what the decision should contain (the Aliens Act, Chapter 13, Section 10) as detailed in the section (7.3).

Similar arguments were presented in relation to the possible introduction of a definition of *vulnerable individuals* or to specifically address their special needs. The government held that existing provisions in Swedish law already adequately met the requirements of the Return Directive on this matter as the Act (2008:344) on Health and Medical Care for Asylum-seekers and Others⁶⁶ extends access to health care not only to asylum seekers but also to, for example, persons who have been granted temporary protection in Sweden (Section 4, Sub-Section 1). Individuals not covered by the aforementioned Act (including irregular migrants or persons who have absconded in order to avoid deportation)

⁶¹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 27–29. Cf. The discussion on terminology in Daniel Thym, *European Migration Law* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2023), 527, where ‘return’ is described as the overarching category and ‘removal’ as the enforcement component.

⁶² Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/2:60, 29.

⁶³ Swedish Parliament, *Terroristbrottslag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2022:666.

⁶⁴ Swedish Parliament, *Lag om särskild kontroll av vissa utlänningar*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2022:700.

⁶⁵ Dir. 2004/38/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the right of citizens of the Union and their family members to move and reside freely within the territory of the Member States amending Regulation (EEC) No 1612/68 and repealing Directives 64/221/EEC, 68/360/EEC, 72/194/EEC, 73/148/EEC, 75/34/EEC, 75/35/EEC, 90/364/EEC, 90/365/EEC and 93/96/EEC.

⁶⁶ Swedish Parliament. *Lag om hälso- och sjukvård åt asylsökande m.fl.*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2008:344.

may still receive immediate health care by the Act on Health and Medical Care for Certain Foreign Nationals Residing in Sweden without Necessary Permits⁶⁷ (2013:407), the Health and Medical Care Act (1982:763)⁶⁸, Section 4, and immediate dental care as specified in the Dental Care Act (1985:125)⁶⁹, Section 6. Additionally, the Social Services Act (2001:453)⁷⁰ and the Health Care Act (2017:30)⁷¹ contain provisions aimed at providing additional support to individuals with special needs. The Aliens Act, Chapter 11, Section 5, Sub-Section 1, grants aliens in immigration detention access to health and medical care. Additionally, the Detention Act⁷², Chapter 5, Section 1, ensures access to health care for inmates when deemed necessary by a medical expert.

Swedish law also does not provide a specific definition for *assisted departure or return*. Instead, as suggested by its title, the Ordinance (1984:890) on Supplements for Foreigners' Travel from Sweden for Settlement in Another Country⁷³, governs financial matters related to aliens' return process to their home country with government support, specifying the conditions and responsible authority.

However, specific new provisions or legislative changes were introduced to meet the requirements associated with each of these defined terms and their respective articles in the Return Directive. Regarding *voluntary departure*, the government, rather than introducing a definition, added new provisions to several Chapters of the Aliens Act, notably Chapters 8 and 12, to regulate the deadline for voluntary departure in line with the Return Directive's requirements.⁷⁴

In its government bill on the implementation of the Return Directive,⁷⁵ the government also highlighted the lack of clearly defined criteria for identifying the risk of absconding. In response, a new provision was introduced into the Aliens Act (Chapter 1, Section 15), aligning Swedish law with the requirement in the Return Directive, Article 3.7. Chapter 1, Section 15 outlines specific situations that can be used to determine the risk of absconding.⁷⁶

A concept not explicitly defined in the Aliens Act but which is of relevance in the context of return is what is referred to as the "*option to change tracks*" (spårbyte). This, in sum, refers to the possibility for an asylum seeker whose application for asylum has been denied and the decision of refusal of entry or expulsion has taken legal effect to, in certain circumstances, apply for a work permit without leaving Sweden (Aliens Act Chapter 5, Section 15 a).⁷⁷ A key requirement is that the asylum seekers must have started working during his/her

⁶⁷ Swedish Parliament, *Lag om hälso- och sjukvård till vissa utlänningar som vistas i Sverige utan nödvändiga tillstånd*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2013:407.

⁶⁸ Swedish Parliament, *Hälso- och sjukvårdslag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 1982:763.

⁶⁹ Swedish Parliament, *Tandvårdslag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 1985:125.

⁷⁰ Swedish Parliament, *Socialtjänstlag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2001:453.

⁷¹ Swedish Parliament, *Hälso- och sjukvårdslag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2017:30.

⁷² Swedish Parliament, *Häktelag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2010:611.

⁷³ Swedish Parliament, *Förordning om bidrag till utlänningars resor från Sverige för bosättning i annat land*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 1984:890.

⁷⁴ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 30. See Section 7.5 of the report for further details.

⁷⁵ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 37.

⁷⁶ See Section 7.5 of the report for further details.

⁷⁷ This also applies if the asylum seeker has had his/her asylum claims reviewed in the first instance but already has received a decision on refusal of entry or expulsion in another case.

time as an asylum seeker. If a work permit is granted, the person in question will also obtain a residence permit and may remain in Sweden. In February 2024, a government commission of inquiry recommended abolishing the 'option to change tracks'.⁷⁸

7.3 Return at Border (Border Rejection), Exit, Internal Check, and Control

7.3.1 General framework

The Aliens Act and the Aliens Ordinance establish a legal framework encompassing various facets of return procedures, including return at border, exit, and internal checks and controls.

The Aliens Act, Chapter 2 outlines the general conditions governing the entry, visit, residence, and work of aliens in Sweden. To enter Sweden, an alien, as a general rule, needs to present a passport, a visa or, when applicable, a residence permit. Exceptions from these requirements are also outlined in the Aliens Act, Chapter 2. Ultimately, however, it is the border police that decide whether a person is allowed to enter Sweden. A person may be rejected at the border even if she has a valid visa or permit, for example, if she/he does not fulfil other requirements, such as necessary vaccinations, such as COVID-19 during the 2020-2022 pandemic.

An alien staying in Sweden for over three months must have a residence permit (Chapter 2, Section 5). The general rule for entry into Sweden stipulates that a residence permit should be applied for and granted prior to entry (Aliens Act Chapter 5, Section 18, Sub-Section 1). The rule allows for several exceptions, for example, for asylum seekers and prolongation of residence permits (see Chapter 5 Section 18, Sub-Sections 2-3, Chapter 5 Section 18 a, and Chapter 5, Section 19.) The Aliens Ordinance indicates specific situations where an alien is not obligated to obtain short-term residence permission (residence permits or visas) to enter Sweden (Chapter 4, Section 6, and Chapter 3, Section 1).

Numerous legislative amendments to the Aliens Act and other relevant legislation concerning entry and exit have been proposed, ratified and eventually enacted to meet the requirements of recent EU regulations in this domain. For instance, these changes encompass the implementation of the European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS)⁷⁹ as specified in Regulation (EU) 2018/1240.⁸⁰ Another notable example is establishing a unified entry and exit system for electronically recording third-country nationals, particularly those with short-term stays or those refused entry when crossing external borders.⁸¹ Furthermore, another recent addition to the legislative framework is the expanded authority to revoke residence permits outlined in the Aliens Act, Chapter 7.⁸² Other legislative

⁷⁸ SOU (Swedish Government Official Reports) 2024:15 Nya regler för arbetskraftsinvandring m.m.

⁷⁹ Prop. (Government Bill). *Anpassning av svensk rätt till EU:s nya system för reseuppgifter och resetillstånd*, 2022/23:66.

⁸⁰ Regulation (EU) 2018/1240 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 September 2018 establishing a European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS) and amending Regulations (EU) No 1077/2011, (EU) No 515/2014, (EU) 2016/399, (EU) 2016/1624 and (EU) 2017/2226.

⁸¹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Anpassning av svensk rätt till EU:s nya in- och utresesystem*, 2021/22:81.

⁸² Prop. (Government Bill), *Anpassningar av svensk lag till EU:s förordningar om Schengens informationssystem*, 2020/21:222, 1.

modifications pertaining to the Schengen Information System (SIS) EU regulations and requirements for foreign individuals to furnish fingerprints and undergo photographic procedures for identity verification within the entry and exit system were also introduced into Swedish law.⁸³

7.3.2 Procedural Safeguards in the Context of the Entry and Exit System in Sweden

While implementing the Return Directive, the Swedish government held that Swedish law retains and upholds the EU return regime's procedural safeguards. The safeguards include postponement of removal, limitations on the use of coercive measures, access to emergency healthcare, consideration for vulnerable individuals, detention conditions, and adherence to the fundamental principle of non-refoulement.⁸⁴ One example of an important procedural safeguard is that a return decision may not be enforced until it has taken legal effect. This means for example that if the Migration Agency has rejected an application for a residence permit (a decision combined with a decision on return) and the decision is appealed to a migration court, the decision does not take legal effect during the appeal process. As a result, it cannot be enforced and the applicant as a general rule may remain in Sweden. The government also held that, in several respects, Swedish law surpasses several of the rights and protections for refugees and asylum seekers stipulated in the Refugee Convention, including Article 33.⁸⁵ Furthermore, the government held that there are no regulations that could lead to the separation of family members following decisions on deportation or expulsion.⁸⁶ Whether this is really the case may be debated.

The Aliens Act incorporates various provisions to establish a legal framework that ensures the principle of non-refoulement and related matters. These provisions are mainly located in Chapter 8, which concerns expulsion and deportation, and Chapter 12, which concerns the execution of decisions on expulsion and deportation. As detailed in the 2012 Swedish government bill on the implementation of the Return Directive, it was determined that no new legislative amendments were required in Swedish law to maintain compliance with the non-refoulement principle, including the postponement of removal decisions by Articles 9 and 5 of the EU Return Directive.⁸⁷

The Aliens Act, Chapter 12 Sections 1–3a lists impediments to enforcing deportation and expulsion decisions. For instance, Chapter 12, Section 1 prohibits the enforcement of such decisions in a country where there is a reasonable risk of death, corporal punishment, torture, or other inhuman or degrading treatment. Similarly, Chapter 12, Section 3 a, stipulates that an unaccompanied minor may only be returned if there are arrangements for their reception by a family member, appointed guardian, or a suitable care facility.

⁸³ Ibid, 1.

⁸⁴ This adherence is explicitly stated in the Swedish Prop. (Government Bill) 2011/12:60, 60-62 concerning the implementation of the Return Directive.

⁸⁵ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 63.

⁸⁶ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 61.

⁸⁷ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 42–43, 60–63.

The Aliens Act mandates the Migration Agency, under Chapter 8, Section 17, to assess asylum applications in the context of deportation enforcement. Chapter 12, Section 18, allows for residence permits in cases of new circumstances that impede the execution of deportation or expulsion, in line with the Aliens Act Chapter 12, Sections 1, 2, 3 and 3a (so-called “political” impediments to the enforcement of a return decision, as Chapter 1-3a) address different aspects of the principle of non-refoulement). Chapter 12 also provides for non-execution of the return decision if the intended receiving country refuses to accept the individual or if medical or other exceptional reasons deem execution inappropriate (Chapter 12, Section 18, Sub-Sections 2 and 3, on practical and medical impediments to enforcement). Furthermore, the Migration Agency may, under Chapter 12, Section 18, Sub-Section 4, suspend deportation and expulsion decisions for re-examination of new facts. If permanent impediments arise, the Aliens Act Chapter 12, Sections 19 and 19a provides, under certain circumstances, for a new residence permit review. Execution of expulsion or deportation decisions is deferred until the Migration Agency or appellate instance concludes this new review. The Aliens Act (Chapter 11, Section 6), the Criminal Code⁸⁸ (Chapter 24, Section 2), and the Police Act⁸⁹ (Section 10), which effectively restricts the use of force during the implementation of coercive measures. It aims to ensure that return procedures are proportional and avoid excessive use of force in compliance with the Return Directive, Article 8.4. Additionally, the government has highlighted the role of various entities in overseeing and protecting the rights of aliens.⁹⁰ These include the administrative courts, the Parliamentary Ombudsman (Justitieombudsmannen), the Chancellor of Justice (Justitiekanslern), the Swedish Migration Agency’s application Ombudsman, and various NGOs, all of which provide avenues for aliens seeking redress. It should also be mentioned that in most relevant cases, Sweden does not utilize the exemptions to implement the Return Directive allowed for member states under the Directive’s Article 2.2 a-b. There are certain exceptions: time limits for voluntary return in the case of denied entry do not apply for individuals mentioned in the Return Directive Article 2.2 a. Also, time limits do not apply to persons who have been issued a return decision by a court as part of their sentence in a criminal trial (the Return Directive Article 2.2 b).⁹¹ The exception in Article 2.2 b is also utilized to permit the Swedish government to make certain decisions concerning detention.

7.4 Regular Procedure to Issue a Return Decision

The regulations about regular procedures for issuing return decisions and their consequences, including re-entry bans and voluntary deportation to Sweden, are primarily established in the Aliens Act and, when applicable, the Act (2022:700) Concerning Special Control of Certain Aliens. The latter Act addresses aliens considered to pose threats to national security. The Migration Agency has the authority to issue expulsion or removal and deportation-related decisions (Chapter 12, Section 14 and Chapter 8, Section 17), which may be appealed to the Migration Court (Chapter 14).⁹² The Police Authority can also, under certain circumstances,

⁸⁸ Swedish Parliament. *Brottsbalken*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 1962: 700.

⁸⁹ Swedish Parliament. *Polislag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 1984: 387.

⁹⁰ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 41.

⁹¹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 33.

⁹² The Migration Agency’s decisions can be appealed to the Migration Courts. The Migration Courts serve as the first instance and are located at four administrative courts in Sweden, namely Stockholm, Malmö, Gothenburg, and Luleå. The final instance for these cases is the Migration Court of Appeal,

issue such decisions (Chapter 12, Section 14 and Chapter 8, Section 17), which may be appealed to the Migration Agency or a Migration Court (Chapter 14). In addition, decisions regarding expulsion due to criminal activity fall under the jurisdiction of the court responsible for the criminal case (Aliens Act, Chapter 8a, Section 10).

The Aliens Act also defines the area of responsibility of the Police Authority concerning the enforcement of expulsion and deportation decisions. This responsibility encompasses the execution of the Police Authority's expulsion and deportation decisions and court decisions for deportation due to criminal activities (Aliens Act, Chapter 12, Section 14). Additionally, it involves enforcing a decision of expulsion and deportation if the alien, after the decision has been enforced once, is found to have returned to Sweden (Chapter 12, Section 23). The Aliens Act, Chapter 8, specifies the various grounds for expulsion and deportation, stating that an alien lacking the necessary permit to stay in Sweden should be expelled or deported, while Chapter 12 details the different aspects of enforcement of expulsion and deportation decisions. For instance, crime or suspected criminality according to the Terrorist Crimes Act (2022:666) and considerations for Sweden's security that can be found in the Act (2022:700) on Special Control of Certain Aliens are stated as grounds for expulsion in the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 1, Sub-Sections 1, 2 and 3). The Security Service enforces expulsion and deportation decisions related to security cases as specified in the Aliens Act (Chapter 12, Section 14) and defined in it (Chapter 1, Section 7).

The Aliens Act outlines the circumstances under which decisions on immediate enforcement can be implemented (Chapter 8, Section 19) and provides instructions for enforcement procedures (Chapter 8, Section 20). It also details when a decision on deportation or expulsion shall be considered executed (Chapter 12, Sections 21 and 22) and when enforcement of a decision has not ceased or is still applicable (Chapter 12, Section 23).

An expulsion and deportation decision must include specific information and be structured as follows: The Aliens Act (Chapter 13, Section 10) mandates that a decision must be in writing and provide the rationale for the decision, especially when it concerns matters such as re-entry bans, expulsions, and deportations. This provision was integrated into the Aliens Act in 2012 to comply with the requirements of Articles 12 and 15.2 of the EU Return Directive.⁹³ In fact, the Administrative Procedure Act (2017:900)⁹⁴ in its Section 20 specifies also that a decision by an authority in any matter involving individual rights shall state the grounds on which it is based. This decision should also outline the potential penalties for violating the re-entry ban as indicated in the Aliens Act (Chapter 8a, Section 10, Sub-Section 2). Additionally, the decision should contain instructions regarding enforcement measures that may be applicable based on the specific circumstances of the individual case, as stipulated in the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 20). Furthermore, the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 27) specifies that certain decisions must be included with expulsion and deportation decisions. This requirement applies even if the affected individual did not initially raise the issues covered by these decisions, or if the issues were not addressed in earlier stages. This includes, for instance, situations like the deportation or expulsion of a child under the age of 16 who is under the custody of an alien subject to return.

which is situated at the Administrative Court of Appeal in Stockholm. For more information, please see the Swedish Courts' website for more information www.domstol.se.

⁹³ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 57.

⁹⁴ Swedish Parliament. *Förvaltningslag*, Svensk författningssamling (SFS) 2017:900.

7.5 Special Cases and their Relation with the Obligation to Issue a Return Decision

7.5.1 Irregular aliens covered by existing bilateral agreements between Member States and holders of a return decision issued by another Member State

Sweden has established several readmission agreements with other EU member states.⁹⁵ Consequently, the Swedish government concluded that Article 6.3 of the Return Directive does not necessitate any legislative amendments within Swedish law.⁹⁶ This conclusion was based on the premise that Article 6.3 grants each member state the option to abstain from issuing a return decision to a third-country national who is residing illegally on its territory. This option is applicable if another Member State readmits that individual under bilateral agreements or arrangements that were in effect when the Directive came into force.⁹⁷ The rationale behind this decision stems from the understanding that these agreements do not supersede the rules of the Aliens Act about decisions on expulsion or deportation. Therefore, there is no requirement to invoke the option of exemption from the obligation to render a decision on deportation or expulsion in this context by Article 6.3.⁹⁸ Consequently, this reasoning is applicable to cases involving individuals holding a return decision issued by another EU member state.

7.5.2 Irregular aliens benefitting from humanitarian (or other) permit/authorisation or subject to a pending procedure renewing a permit/authorisation

The Aliens Act encompasses legislative provisions pertinent to aliens present in Sweden under irregular conditions or without a valid residence permit. This scenario extends to individuals engaged in the renewal of their permits or those benefitting from humanitarian or alternative forms of authorization, as delineated in Articles 6.4 and 6.5 of the Return Directive.⁹⁹

Diverse clauses within the Aliens Act articulate that any decision regarding deportation or expulsion becomes null or unenforceable when the individual possesses a valid residence permit. This is particularly relevant for aliens who, subsequent to being issued a deportation order, are subsequently granted a residence permit. The Aliens Act (Chapter 5, Sections 18 and 19) implicitly affords a right to foreign nationals who have filed for an extension of their residence permits to legally reside in Sweden for the duration of the processing period of their application.¹⁰⁰ Consequently, such individuals are exempt from expulsion or deportation during this interim. The government, thus, in the government bill on the implementation of

⁹⁵ See Section 7.11 of this report.

⁹⁶ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 29.

⁹⁷ *Ibid.*

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹⁹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 28.

¹⁰⁰ *Ibid.*

the EU Return Directive, interpreted these sections as complying with the Directive's mandate for the revocation or temporary postponement of return decisions upon the issuance of a residence permit.¹⁰¹

Moreover, as is also emphasized in the government bill, under Article 6.4 all Member States are vested with the prerogative to issue a residence permit or any alternative authorisation for residency at any given juncture. This discretion is manifest in the Aliens Act, particularly in Chapter 12, Section 18, which stipulates the potential for an alien to be granted a residence permit under new circumstances that pertain to the execution of a legally binding decision on expulsion or deportation or in instances where such a decision is subject to suspension.

7.5.3 Irregular aliens which can be transferred to another Member State under Dublin rules (or under readmission rules)

The Aliens Act, Chapter 1, Section 9, specifies that the regulations regarding expulsion and deportation decisions, as outlined in the Act, also apply to Dublin transfer decisions directed to the responsible Member State.¹⁰² The Aliens Act, Chapter 5, Section 1 b stipulates in which cases an asylum application may be rejected, and under which conditions. The provision implements the Asylum Procedures Directive (recast), Article 33.2 a.¹⁰³ The Aliens Act, Chapter 5, Section 1 c, Sub-section 1 stipulates that transfer decisions for asylum seekers are conducted in compliance with the Dublin Regulation, extending to EU member states as well as Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, and Liechtenstein. Chapter 5, Section 1 c, Sub-Section 2 stipulates that an asylum application shall be rejected in the case of a Dublin transfer. The provision implements the Asylum Procedures Directive (recast), Article 33.1. If the applicant claims a need for international protection concerning the state responsible for the asylum application due to the Dublin Regulation, the Migration Court of Appeal has concluded that what is to be assessed is if the transfer may constitute a violation of the principle of non-refoulement (see MIG 2010:21 and MIG 2016:16).

The Aliens Act, Chapter 12, Section 9 a, stipulates that if a decision on transferring an alien following the Dublin Regulation has been appealed, and during the period of appeal, a request for the suspension of the decision has been made, the transfer decision shall not be executed until a migration court has examined the issue of suspension. This applies only the first time the foreign national requests suspension. A decision to deny such a request for suspension must be duly justified.¹⁰⁴

Swedish case law has had a significant impact on the application of the Dublin Regulation. An example is the judgment of the Migration Court of Appeal, MIG 2006:4, which established that once a transfer decision has been made under the Dublin Regulation, there is

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Cf. Prop. (Government Bill) *Ändringar i utlänningslagen med anledning av den omarbetade Dublinförordningens ikraftträdande*, 2013/14:197; Prop. (Government Bill) *Ytterligare anpassning av svensk rätt till Dublinförordningen*, 2016/17:150. and Prop. (Government Bill) *Genomförande av skyddsgrundsdirektivet och asylprocedurdirektivet*, 2009/10:31, 216.

¹⁰³ Prop. (Government Bill), *Ändringar i utlänningslagen med anledning av den omarbetade Dublinförordningens ikraftträdande*, 2013/14:197.

¹⁰⁴ Prop. (Government Bill), *Ytterligare anpassning av svensk rätt till Dublinförordningen*, 2016/17:150.

no possibility to review the asylum application in Sweden. A second example is the judgment of the Migration Court of Appeal, MIG 2014:29, which determined that the provisions on legal aid in the Aliens Act (Chapter 18, Section 1) could be applied to cases concerning transfer issues under the Dublin Regulation if the need for legal assistance is deemed necessary.

7.5.4 Irregular aliens with a right to stay in another Member State

In late 2016, the Swedish government proposed legislative amendments to the Aliens Act to, to a more considerable extent, align Swedish migration law with the Return Directive and the Directive governing the status of third-country nationals as Permanent Residents.¹⁰⁵ The proposals resulted in the introduction of new provisions into the Aliens Act. The Aliens Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a addresses the expulsion and deportation of individuals who meet the following criteria: (1) are not EEA nationals or family members of EEA nationals, (2) possess a residence permit from another EU state, but (3) do not meet the requirements for staying in Sweden under the Aliens Act, Chapter 8, and (4) are subject to deportation or expulsion from Sweden under the same Chapter of the Aliens Act. The provisions outlined in the Return Directive, Article 6.2, made this legislative amendment necessary. Notably, during discussions on Sweden's implementation of the Return Directive, the European Commission pointed out in a memorandum the absence of specific regulations governing the expulsion and deportation procedures for the category of aliens addressed here.¹⁰⁶ These persons are to, following the first subsection of the Aliens Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a, to be instructed by the deciding authority to voluntarily proceed to the other EU state within a reasonable time. The instruction may not be appealed because it is considered a decision in favour of the alien (it is not enforceable). The deciding authority may only determine the issue of removal or expulsion if the foreign national has not complied with such an instruction. The Aliens Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a, Sub-section 2 however stipulates that the first subsection does not apply in the following cases:

1. The Migration Agency rejects or denies an application for a residence permit which, according to the provisions of this Act or any other legislation, may be granted after entry into Sweden.
2. The alien is denied entry into the country.
3. The alien is intercepted in the act of illegally crossing an external border.
4. The alien poses a risk to public order and security.
5. It is deemed probable that the alien would not comply with the instruction.

In April 2023, the CJEU in the case C-629/22 (which concerned Sweden and the validity of the Aliens Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a, subsection 2) found that the Return Directive, Article 6.2, requires states to provide irregular aliens with the possibility to return to the member state in which they hold a residence permit before the national authorities issue a decision on return.¹⁰⁷ The CJEU, in the judgment, concludes (without saying so explicitly) that the Aliens

¹⁰⁵Prop. (Government Bill), *Uppföljning av återvändandenedirektivet och direktivet om varaktigt bosatta tredjelandsmedborgares ställning*, 2016/17:61.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid, 14.

¹⁰⁷ CJEU, C-629/22, ECLI:EU:C:2023:365.

Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a, subsection 2 does not fully comply with the Return Directive, Article 6.2. So far, however, the legislation remains unchanged.

7.6 Voluntary Departure

The relevant regulations concerning voluntary return and the consequence of their non-compliance, which is “re-entry bans”, have undergone multiple legislative amendments in the Aliens Act since the implementation of the Return Directive in May 2012, particularly the deadline of the voluntary return. This aspect aligns with the legislative change required by the EU Return Directive, Article 7. The matter of voluntary return was acknowledged as central due to its impact on the execution of other articles within the Return Directive and eventually on the entire return regime by the Swedish government.¹⁰⁸ Consequently, the Aliens Act establishes a general rule (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 1) concerning the inclusion of a deadline for voluntary departure and re-entry bans in expulsion or deportation decisions, along with exceptional rules (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 2) in some instances and situations where this voluntary departure deadline cannot be given in the expulsion or deportation decisions. Accordingly, a decision of expulsion or deportation must include a timeframe within which the alien must leave Sweden voluntarily (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 1) as a general rule. The voluntary departure deadline can be set for up to two weeks in the case of expulsion and four weeks in the case of deportation by the Aliens Act regulations (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 1). The Migration Court of Appeal in MIG 2021:13 declared that no coercive measures may be taken against a foreign national to ensure the enforcement of a removal order while the period for voluntary departure is running.

For EEA citizens or their family members who have travelled in Sweden, different rules apply to the voluntary return deadline or departure. The Aliens Act states that an EEA citizen or their family members shall be granted no earlier than four weeks from the day the EEA citizen or family member received the decision unless there are exceptional reasons for implementing the decision (Chapter 12, Section 15, Sub-Section 3). This provision aligns with the requirement of Article 30.3 in the Citizen's Rights Directive (2004/38/EC).¹⁰⁹

The deadline for voluntary departure can be extended if special reasons exist (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 1). This provision corresponds with the Return Directive, Article 7.2, which provides several examples of specific circumstances in individual cases, “such as the length of stay, the existence of children attending school, and the existence of other family and social ties”.¹¹⁰ However, the Swedish government determined that the circumstances warranting an extension of the voluntary departure deadline should not be specified in the new provision, as an extension should be possible if required.¹¹¹

This extension for the voluntary return deadline is determined by the Migration Agency or the Policy Authority (Chapter 12, Section 14b). Additionally, the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 2) lists specific situations where a voluntary return deadline need not be included in deportation and expulsion decisions based on five grounds: i) there is a risk that alien will abscond; ii) the alien poses a threat to public order and security; iii) a deportation

¹⁰⁸ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 31.

¹⁰⁹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 33.

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ Ibid.

decision denies the alien entry into the country; iv) the alien is intercepted while illegally crossing an external border and is subsequently deported *or* v) the alien is deported by the Migration Agency with immediate execution.

These grounds correspond with the Return Directive, Article 7.4.¹¹² The concept of a "risk of absconding" was recognized as central in this context as it impacts the implementation of several articles in the Return Directive, including voluntary return, re-entry bans, and detention, and eventually the main objective of precise whole implementation of the Return Directive.¹¹³ As a result a provision was incorporated into the Aliens Act (Chapter 1, Section 15) specifying its meaning or circumstances as follows:

‘If, in the application of this Act, an assessment is made as to whether there is a risk of an alien absconding, considerations may only be given if he or she:

- has previously evaded authorities,
- has declared an intention not to leave the country after an expulsion decision,
- has used a false identity,
- has not cooperated in clarifying their identity, thereby hindering the examination of their residence permit application,
- has knowingly provided false information or withheld material information,
- has violated an announced re-entry ban in the past,
- has been convicted of a crime punishable by imprisonment or
- has been expelled by a general court based on criminal grounds.’

On the matter of financial support in the context of return, the special Ordinance (1984:890) addresses financial support for an alien's travel from Sweden to resettle in another country. This ordinance designates the Migration Agency to determine government grants for the following categories:

Aliens granted residence permits in Sweden based on government transfer;

Aliens granted residence permits in Sweden for protection reasons, per the Aliens Act, Chapter 5);

Aliens granted residence permits in Sweden due to their connection to those in the previous categories 1 or 2, not eligible for assistance under Swedish law.

Sections 3 and 5 of this Ordinance specify that this grant is disbursed when the recipient departs Sweden, provided they lack the means for the journey and can show they will be received in their intended settlement country.

An alien whose asylum application has been rejected or who has withdrawn their asylum application may also, under certain circumstances, apply for financial (cash) support to help re-establish in the country of return.¹¹⁴ The process and conditions are regulated by the Ordinance (2008:778) on re-establishment support for certain aliens. The cash support is

¹¹² Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 37.

¹¹³ Ibid.

¹¹⁴ For more information on to which countries the support applies, see <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Privatpersoner/Lamna-Sverige/Avslag-pa-ansokan-om-asyl/Stod-till-ateretablering/Kontantstod.html> (last accessed Januari 2, 2024).

made available to the alien in the country of return. There is also a possibility to apply for reintegration measures in the context of the European collaboration programme Joint Reintegration Service (JRS).¹¹⁵

7.7 Return of Unaccompanied Minors

The Aliens Act, Chapter 1, Section 1 a) states that "child" for the purpose of the Act refers to a person below the age of 18. The Aliens Act Chapter 1, Section 10 and Chapter 1, Section 11 implement two fundamental principles of the Convention on the Rights of the Child into the Act: the best-interests principle and the right to be heard. The two provisions were introduced in the Aliens Act in 1997 as part of the efforts to transform key parts of the CRC into Swedish law.¹¹⁶ The Aliens Act, Chapter 1, Section 10 mandates the consideration of a child's health, development, and overall best interests in all cases related to children and is based on Articles 3.1 and 6 of the CRC.¹¹⁷ The Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 11 mandates that when assessing questions related to a residence permit under the Aliens Act, and when the decision impacts a child, the child must be heard unless it is deemed inappropriate. Account must be taken of what the child has said to the extent warranted by the age and maturity of the child. Chapter 1, Section 11 is based on Article 12 of the CRC. Both Chapter 1, Section 10 and Chapter 1, Section 11 apply in deportation and expulsion cases. Moreover, it may be noted that the right to oral proceedings in asylum cases, as outlined in the Aliens Act, Chapter 13, Section 1, applies to adults and children alike. When implementing the Asylum Procedures Directive (recast) into Swedish law, the government concluded that there was no need for legislative amendments to specifically require child-oriented interviews with minors, given the fact that the right to be heard as well as the best-interests principle were already included in the Aliens Act.¹¹⁸

While the Aliens Act does not contain a specific definition of unaccompanied minors (UAMs), it is recognized in Swedish migration law that UAMs are entitled to special protection.¹¹⁹ The "Reception of Asylum Seekers and Others Act" stipulates that special conditions apply to UAMs, for example regarding housing.¹²⁰ Moreover, the Unaccompanied Minors Guardian Act (2005:429) states that the interests of UAMs are to be protected through the appointment of a special guardian ("*god man*"). The special guardian acts instead of the child's parents or legal guardian and thus has a different role than the child's legal representative. Following the Aliens Act, Chapter 18, Section 1 a, a public legal counsel shall always be appointed to a child seeking asylum in Sweden if the child does not have a legal guardian in Sweden. The same applies to children appealing a negative decision on asylum or on impediments of enforcement. The right to public legal counsel also applies to children who

¹¹⁵ Ibid.

¹¹⁶ Prop. (Government Bill), *Svensk migrationspolitik i globalt perspektiv*, 1996/97:25. See also Section 4 of the report.

¹¹⁷ The Migration Court of Appeal has discussed the interpretation and implementation of the best interests-principle in several judgments, including MIG 2020:24 and MIG 2021:18.

¹¹⁸ Genomförande av det omarbetade asylprocedurdirektivet, Prop. (Government Bill) 2016/17:17, 50.

¹¹⁹ The Aliens Act however refers to this group in various terms, such as the reference to "children who have arrived in Sweden separated from their parents or another adult having effectively taken the parent's place, or if the child has been abandoned after arrival" in the Aliens Act, Chapter 5, Section 3. The matter of age assessments, in order to determine whether a person claiming to be a child actually is below the age of 18, is addressed in the Aliens Act Chapter 13, Sections 17 and 18, and in the Aliens Ordinance, Chapter 4, Section 21 d.

¹²⁰ Section 1 b of the Reception of Asylum Seekers and Others Act.

have been assigned a special guardian according to the Unaccompanied Minors Guardian Act (2005:429).¹²¹

The Aliens Act, in addition to the overarching provisions pertaining to the right to be heard and the best interests principle in Chapter 1 of the Act, also includes specific provisions addressing the rights of unaccompanied minors in the context of return.¹²² Chapter 12, Section 3 a establishes that a decision to deport or expel an unaccompanied minor cannot be enforced unless the enforcing authority ensures that the child will be received by a family member, an appointed guardian, or a reception unit well-equipped to care for children. If these requirements are not met, the return decision cannot be enforced – there is what is referred to as a practical impediment to the enforcement of the decision (see Section 7.2.2 above). In these cases, the UAM will usually be granted a temporary residence permit valid until he or she turns 18 based on the Aliens Act Chapter 5, Section 11. The Migration Court of Appeal in MIG 2015:23 emphasized that the Migration Agency has a special responsibility for unaccompanied minors, including in the return process, and that the Migration Agency has the primary responsibility for ensuring that the reception conditions in the country of origin are adequate, even though the child is expected to contribute to the process.¹²³ Also in MIG 2015:23, the Migration Court of Appeal on the matter of re-entry bans held that, as the child in question was found to have contributed to the return process as best she could, the requirements for not applying a re-entry ban (as stipulated in the Aliens Act Chapter 12, Section 15 a) were fulfilled.

While the Aliens Act and adjacent legislation on paper provide for safeguarding the special needs of UAMs in Sweden, this, as has been continuously pointed out by NGO-s and migration scholars, has not always translated into practice.¹²⁴

The 2016 introduction of temporary residence permits in combination with the increased focus on return, while simultaneously remaining to be difficult to enforce return decisions, has resulted in many non-citizens, including UAMs or young adults, becoming stuck in legal limbo, often living under challenging economic and social circumstances.¹²⁵ In addition, the normalization of an immigration-critical (or immigration-hostile) discourse has contributed to their difficult situation and to justifying repeal of legislation aimed at safeguarding their rights (such as the Upper Secondary School Act and humanitarian grounds in the Aliens Act Chapter 5 Section 6, Sub-Section 2).¹²⁶

¹²¹ Migration Court of Appeal judgment MIG 2015:23.

¹²² See also CJEU, C-484/22, February 15, 2023, ECLI:EU: C:2023:122.

¹²³ See also CJEU, C-C-441/19, January 14, 2021; ECLI:EU:C:2021:9.

¹²⁴ Barnombudsmannen, *Barn på flykt. Barns och ungas röster om mottagandet av ensamkommande* (Stockholm, Barnombudsmannen, 2017); Swedish Red Cross, *Mitt liv räknas – den humanitära situationen för ensamkommande unga* (Stockholm, Svenska Röda Korset, 2020); Daniel Hedlund, *Drawing the Limits. Unaccompanied Minors in Swedish Asylum Policy and Procedure*, dissertation (Stockholm, Stockholm University, 2016); Marianne Garvik and Marco Valenta, “Seeking Asylum in Scandinavia: A Comparative Analysis of Recent Restrictive Policy Responses Towards Unaccompanied Afghan Minors in Denmark, Sweden and Norway,” *Comparative Migration Studies*, Vol. 9, Issue 1 (2021): 1-22.

¹²⁵ Garvik and Valenta, *Seeking Asylum in Scandinavia: A Comparative Analysis of Recent Restrictive Policy Responses Towards Unaccompanied Afghan Minors in Denmark, Sweden and Norway*.

¹²⁶ Amber Horning, Sara V. Jordanö and Nicole Savoie, “Double-Edged Risk: Unaccompanied Minor Refugees (UMRs) in Sweden and Their Search for Safety,” *Journal of Refugee Studies*, Vol. 33, No. 2, June (2020): 390–415.

7.8 Re-Entry Bans

To implement the provisions on entry bans from the Return Directive into Swedish law, numerous revisions and amendments have been made to the Aliens Act.¹²⁷ These amendments tie the regulation of entry bans closely to the regulation of timeframes for voluntary return, as discussed in Section 7.5. According to the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 23), if it proves impossible to set a timeframe for voluntary departure the decision on expulsion by the Police Authority and the decisions on rejection, expulsion, or deportation by the Migration Agency must include a re-entry ban. This is unless specific circumstances relating to the individual's situation warrant otherwise. This requirement is contingent upon the absence of conditions for setting a voluntary departure deadline based on the five criteria detailed in the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 21, Sub-Section 2).

The Aliens Act, Chapter 8, Section 24 mandates that the duration of an entry ban based on Chapter 8, Section 23 typically should not surpass five years, except in cases where the individual poses a significant risk to public order and security, which may justify a longer ban. For aliens who fail to comply with an expulsion or deportation decision and remain in Sweden past the voluntary departure period, the re-entry ban is set to one year (Chapter 12, Section 15a). In early February 2024, a Government Inquiry suggested that the duration of entry-bans based on Chapter 12, Section 15 a should be based on an individual assessment of the case in question, something which might lead to longer entry bans for this category.¹²⁸ It is also suggested that it should be specifically stated in the Aliens Act that a re-entry ban not issued by a general court shall commence on the day the alien leaves the territory of the Member States or, if the decision on expulsion or deportation is to be enforced to a Member State, on the day the he or she exits Sweden.¹²⁹ Should these proposals become law, they are to enter into force in 2025.

The Aliens Act differentiates between re-entry bans resulting from criminal conduct (Chapter 8a) and those due to non-criminal reasons (Chapter 8). In the context of criminal activities, the duration of a re-entry ban may be specified or indefinite, as outlined in the Aliens Act (Chapter 8a, Section 11, Sub-Section 1). Recent legislative updates to the Aliens Act and the Penal Code have facilitated the deportation of individuals who commit crimes and have introduced stricter regulations on deportation for criminal activities.¹³⁰ These amendments, effective from 1 August 2022, have extended the length of re-entry bans, which now commence on the day of departure.

Notably, specific rules apply to re-entry bans for EEA citizens and their family members. Only decisions concerning public order or security can result in a re-entry ban for an EEA citizen or their relative, in accordance with the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 23). This provision, adopted in 2006, aligns with Article 15.1 and 3 of the EU Free Movement Directive,

¹²⁷ Cf. Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60; Prop. (Government Bill), *Uppföljning av återvändandedirektivet och direktivet om varaktigt bosatta tredjelandsmedborgares ställning*, 2016/17:61 and Prop. (Government Bill), *Utvisning på grund av brott – ett skärpt regelverk*, 2021/22:224.

¹²⁸ Preskription av avlägsnandebeslut och vissa frågor om återreseförbud, SOU 2024:10 (Chapter 6.3).

¹²⁹ Ibid.

¹³⁰ Prop. (Government Bill), *Utvisning på grund av brott – ett skärpt regelverk*, 2021/22:224.

highlighting the necessity to avoid imposing re-entry bans on EU citizens and their family members for reasons beyond public order or security.¹³¹

Furthermore, the Aliens Act (Chapter 8, Section 26, Subsection 1) allows for the Migration Agency, the Migration Court, and the Migration Court of Appeal to wholly or partially revoke a re-entry ban if special circumstances indicate the ban is no longer appropriate. The government bill on the implementation of the Return Directive provides examples, such as considerations of the best interests of children, which could warrant the lifting of a re-entry ban. The legislation also offers a mechanism for the affected individual or the Migration Agency to request the lifting of a ban (Chapter 8, Section 26, Sub-Sections 2 and 3). The Aliens Act links the enforceability of expulsion or deportation decisions to the imposition of re-entry bans, specifying that a re-entry ban cannot be notified if the execution of an expulsion or deportation decision is hindered by a stay of execution, an application for a residence permit, or a re-evaluation request (Chapter 12, Section 15a, Sub-Section 2).

7.9 Procedural Safeguards in the Context of Return Enforcement

The Swedish return regime includes several procedural safeguards, demonstrated throughout this report. However, some aspects of this procedural safeguard regime remain to be summarized in this section. When first implementing the EU Return Directive, the government concluded that legislative amendments were unnecessary since the existing provisions in Swedish law met the criteria set out in the Directive Articles 12.1, 12.2, 12.3, 13.3, and 13.4.¹³² For instance, when dealing with individuals who do not speak Swedish, it is incumbent upon an authority to engage an interpreter if necessary, ensuring that documents are translated to enable the person to exercise their rights, as stipulated in the Administrative Act (FL 2017:900) Section 13. Moreover, both the Administrative Court Procedure Act (FPL, 1971:291) Section 50¹³³ and the Act of Judicial Procedure (RB 1942:740) Section 5, Sub-Section 6 guarantee linguistic assistance by appointing an interpreter when needed if a party, witness, or any other individual to be heard in court does not speak Swedish. These provisions regarding interpreters also encompass the translation of documents, encompassing both incoming documents and those prepared by the Migration Agency.

The Aliens Act provides a mechanism for offering public legal aid in the form of public legal counsel in certain situations or under particular conditions for aliens. These situations encompass cases involving deportation and expulsion decisions. Importantly, this legal assistance is provided without charge and is not subject to means-testing, meaning that foreign nationals are not obligated to reimburse any associated costs.¹³⁴ It should also be highlighted that the right to legal representation under the Aliens Act extends more broadly than the right to legal aid stipulated by the Asylum Procedures Directive. This expanded scope is due to the presumption rule outlined in the Aliens Act Chapter 18, Section 1. As a result of this rule, a legal counsel is appointed in nearly all cases of expulsion, deportation, and

¹³¹ Gerhard Wikrén and Håkan Sandesjö, *Utlänningslagen med kommentarer*, 13A ed. JUNO (digital edition).

¹³² Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 59.

¹³³ Swedish Parliament. *Förvaltningsprocesslag*, Svenska författningssamling (SFS) 1971:291

¹³⁴ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 68.

enforcement proceedings involving the detention of an alien.¹³⁵ It follows by Chapter 18, Section 1 that the appointment of a legal counsel is mandatory, except when it can be reasonably assumed that there is no need for legal assistance.

7.10 Basic Conditions for Return Enforcement Detention in Sweden

(Immigration) detention (*förvar*) and the less restrictive measure of supervision (*uppsikt*) are regulated in the Aliens Act. Chapters 10 and 11 of the Aliens Act outline the conditions under which these coercive measures may be used (Chapter 10) and the minimum standards according to which a detainee is to be treated (Chapter 11). The Act (2022:700) on special control of certain Aliens regulates detention in security cases. The Aliens Act Chapter 1 Section 8 stipulates that the Aliens Act ‘shall be applied to ensure an alien’s freedom is not restricted more than is necessary in each individual case’. The proportionality principle expressed here also applies to detention and supervision.¹³⁶ As a consequence of the proportionality principle, detention should only be used in cases where supervision is not considered sufficient.¹³⁷ The conditions for putting a person under supervision are outlined in the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Sections 6 and 7. The Migration Court of Appeal in MIG 2020:2 established that for supervision to be used instead of detention, there must be a basis for detention according to the Aliens Act, which is compatible with EU law. Chapter 1, Section 8 and Chapter 10, Section 6 combined are found to fulfil the requirement of using alternative sufficient but less intrusive measures as specified in the Return Directive, Article 15.1. Sweden, however, has been repeatedly criticized for not using detention as a last resort, but rather as a first choice.¹³⁸

It is noteworthy that although the grounds for detention in EU directives such as the Return Directive, Reception Conditions Directive, and the Asylum Procedures Directive target different categories of third-country nationals and thus differ, the same distinction is not made in the Aliens Act Chapter 10; these rules apply to all third-country nationals. The Migration Court of Appeal in MIG 2020:2 emphasized that while the Swedish regulations on detention form the basis for detention, they must be interpreted and applied in a manner compatible with EU law. It can be added that the same applies to the ECHR, Article 5.1 f in particular, and also the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights.

The Aliens Act, Chapter 10, Section 1 regulates the circumstances under which an adult may be detained. Chapter 10, Section 1, Sub-Section 3 outlines the requirements for a person to be detained for return: that is, either to prepare for the enforcement of a return decision or actual enforcement of such a decision (*verkställighetsförvar*). When the Return Directive was implemented into Swedish law in 2012, the primary conditions for detention for removal in the Aliens Act were modified in order to align with the requirements of the Directive, Articles 15 and 16 in particular.¹³⁹ Revisions included specifying under which circumstances a person can be detained for this purpose (see Chapter 10, Section 1, Sub-Section 4). These are now limited to when there may otherwise be a risk that the alien engages in criminal activities

¹³⁵ Ibid.

¹³⁶ Andersson, ”Förvar och principerna för tvång,” *Juridisk Tidskrift*, No.2 (2020): 367–405.

¹³⁷ On supervision, see *the Aliens Act* Chapter 10, Sections 6 to 8.

¹³⁸ CCPR/C/SWE/CO/7, p. 33; CAT/C/SWE/CO/6-7, p. 10.

¹³⁹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 70.

within Sweden, will evade the authorities, go into hiding or otherwise obstruct the execution of the return decision.¹⁴⁰ While “otherwise engaging in criminal activities” is not one of the grounds for detention listed in Article 15.1 of the Return Directive, the Swedish position is that the wording of Article 15.1 is not exhaustive and thus allows for additional grounds to be included in national legislation.¹⁴¹

In order to align the Aliens Act with the Return Directive's Articles 15.1, 15.5, and 15.6, new time limitations for detention were introduced in the Aliens Act in 2012.¹⁴² Consequently, the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 4, Sub-Section 2 stipulates that an alien aged 18 or older should not be detained for enforcement purposes for more than two months unless compelling reasons warrant a longer duration. Even if there are compelling reasons, the alien must not be detained for more than three months unless enforcement is likely to take longer due to the alien's non-cooperation or the time needed to obtain necessary documents, in which case the detention should not exceed twelve months. However, the three and twelve-month time limits do not apply if the foreign national has been expelled by a criminal court due to criminal offences, in which case detention may be more prolonged.¹⁴³ Article 2.2 b of the Return Directive allows for such exceptions.¹⁴⁴

Children may also be taken into detention or put under supervision for return. The Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 2, Sub-Section 1 stipulates that a child may be detained under the following circumstances: if it is probable that the child will be expelled by the Police Authority or deported with immediate effect by the Migration Agency or if it concerns preparing or executing the enforcement of such a decision, there is a clear risk that the child will otherwise abscond, thereby jeopardizing enforcement that should not be delayed, and it is insufficient for the child to be placed under supervision. In addition, a child may be put in detention to prepare or enforce a return decision in cases other than those above if previous attempts to enforce the decision have proven insufficient to place the child under supervision (see the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 2, Sub-Section 2). Under the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 5, a child may not be detained for more than 72 hours or, if exceptional grounds apply, for another 72 hours. Chapter 10, Section 3 stipulates that a child must not be separated from both of its guardians by detaining either the child or the guardian. A child who does not have a guardian in Sweden may only be detained for exceptional reasons – in other words, UAMs may be put in detention, but only under very particular circumstances.

Not all of the provisions on detention of the Return Directive have been implemented into the Aliens Act. This is as the government, in the process of implementing the Return Directive into Swedish legislation, concluded that existing national legislation already met many of the requirements outlined in the Return Directive Articles 15, 16, and 17.¹⁴⁵ Such requirements include the EU provisions on review of detention decisions, immediate release, decision-making authorities and conditions of detention.¹⁴⁶

¹⁴⁰ Andersson, ”Förvar och principerna för tvång.”

¹⁴¹ Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 69–72. See also the discussion in Andersson, ”Förvar och principerna för tvång,” 374–375.

¹⁴² Prop. (Government Bill), *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 2011/12:60, 74–75.

¹⁴³ *Ibid*, 74.

¹⁴⁴ *Ibid*, 76.

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid*, 69–71.

¹⁴⁶ *Ibid*, 69–71.

Detention-related decisions can, as stipulated in the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Sections 12-17, be made by the Police Authority, the Migration Agency, the Security Police, the Migration Courts, and the Migration Court of Appeal. In security cases, the Swedish government may also make decisions on detention as provided for in the Act (2022:700) on special control of certain Aliens, which regulates detention in security cases. As follows by the Aliens Act Chapter 16, Section 4, detention cases shall be expedited. There is, however, no specific time limit set for this matter.¹⁴⁷

Decisions by the Migration Agency, the Police Authority and the Security Police can be appealed to a Migration Court (the Aliens Act Chapter 14 Section 9). No time limits apply to such appeals. Additionally, the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 9, Sub-Section 1 specifies that a decision on detention shall be re-evaluated within two weeks from the commencement of enforcement. If the alien is detained due to an expulsion or deportation decision, a new review shall be conducted continuously within two months of enforcement's commencement. Chapter 10, Section 9, Sub-Section 4 stipulates that a detention decision should be immediately revoked if there are no longer sufficient grounds for the decision.

The Migration Agency is responsible for enforcing decisions on detention (the Aliens Act Chapter 10, Section 18). It may, for this purpose, request assistance from the Policy Authority. Detention shall, as stated in the Aliens Act Chapter 11, Section 2, take place in facilities designated explicitly for the purpose. The Migration Agency is responsible for these facilities. In late 2023 the Migration Agency had a total capacity for detaining approximately 567 individuals. This capacity is distributed across six locations: Gävle, Flen, Ljungbyhed, Märsta, Mölndal, and Åstorp. The capacity for detaining individuals is expected to increase in the coming years with capacity for approximately another 200 individuals.¹⁴⁸

The Migration Agency may, however, decide that an alien taken into detention is placed in a penitentiary, remand centre, or police custody (the Aliens Act Chapter 10 Section 20). This may be the case when a criminal court expels the alien due to criminal offences or when special reasons apply. In any case, the regulations of the Aliens Act, Chapter 11 on the conditions of detention apply, as well as relevant provisions of the Detention Act (as stated in the Aliens Act Chapter 11, Section 2).¹⁴⁹

Chapter 11, Section 1 of the Aliens Act emphasizes humane treatment and respect for the dignity of the detained individual. The detainee must be informed of their rights, and activities related to detention should be designed to infringe minimally on their privacy and rights (as stipulated in the Return Directive Article 16.5). The Migration Agency is responsible for treating and supervising detainees (Chapter 11, Section 2). Chapter 11, Section 3 states that detainees should have activities, recreation, physical exercise, and outdoor time opportunities. Children in detention should have access to play and age-appropriate activities. Whether this is the case in practice has been questioned, for example, in a 2018 report by the Swedish Red Cross.¹⁵⁰ The conditions in Swedish detention centres on several occasions have been criticized, including by the Parliamentary Ombudsmen, for not living up to the standards established by the Aliens Act, Chapter 11, Section 1. Examples of misconduct has included

¹⁴⁷ Ibid, 77.

¹⁴⁸ Migrationsverket, Skrivelse, drn 1.1.1.2-2023-17747, Redovisning av uppdragen i regleringsbrev för 2022 och 2023 om plan för utökad förvarskapacitet och ytterligare förvarsplatser.

¹⁴⁹ See also [the Detention Act](#), Chapter 2, Section 2.

¹⁵⁰ Swedish Red Cross, *Barn i förvar – en undersökning av Svenska Röda Korset*, Swedish Red Cross 2018.

access to health care for detainees, the conduct of employees towards detainees, and unlawful body searches.¹⁵¹

Under certain conditions, detainees may, according to Chapter 11, Section 4, receive visits and correspondence. They may also be separated from other detainees (Chapter 11, Section 7). Chapter 11, Section 7 mandates that families in detention be offered separate accommodation. All decisions regarding the treatment of detainees can typically be appealed.

7.11 Emergency situations

The Swedish government has opted not to pursue legislative amendments to implement the provisions in Article 18 of the Return Directive. Article 18 allows for exceptions in implementing certain detention-related provisions, particularly in scenarios involving exceptionally high numbers of third-country nationals subject to deportation or expulsion decisions.¹⁵² The first option under Article 18 permits the extension of time limits for judicial reviews in detention cases, as outlined in Article 15.2. However, the Swedish government found that Swedish law already had this possibility or flexibility in its legal framework. This was specifically evident in the Aliens Act (Chapter 4, Section 16), which addressed the need for expeditious handling of detention cases, though without specifying a particular time limit.¹⁵³ The second option in Article 18 pertains to taking emergency measures regarding detention conditions, allowing deviations from the provisions in Article 16.1 related to access to legal representatives, family members, and relevant organizations. However, the Aliens Act, specifically Chapter 11, Section 2, Sub-Section 1, already provides the flexibility to address situations envisioned in Article 18 of the directive concerning the requirements of Article 16.1.¹⁵⁴ Additionally, the government has opted not to exercise the third option or exception in Article 18, which relates to deviations from the requirement in Article 17.2 regarding family detention with separate accommodation ensuring sufficient privacy. Consequently, the Aliens Act (Chapter 11, Section 2, Sub-Section 1) continues to mandate that detained aliens be housed in specially designated premises. This includes facilities established by the Migration Agency in reception centres or other locations, as well as facilities provided or arranged by the Migration Agency, such as hotel rooms.¹⁵⁵

¹⁵¹ Cf. Justitieombudsmannen (Riksdagens ombudsmän, the Parliamentary Ombudsmen), OPCAT Inspection Protocol No. O 3-2023, Inspection 17-18 January 2023 of the Migration Agency detention centre in Mölndal; Justitieombudsmannen (Riksdagens ombudsmän, the Parliamentary Ombudsmen), Decision No. 9303-2022, 12 December, 2023, Justitieombudsmannen (Riksdagens ombudsmän, the Parliamentary Ombudsmen), Decision No. 1432-2018, 3 December 2019; Justitieombudsmannen (Riksdagens ombudsmän, the Parliamentary Ombudsmen), Decision No. 6090-2009, May 19, 2011.

¹⁵² Prop. (Government Bill). *Genomförande av återvändandedirektivet*, 12:60, 78–81.

¹⁵³ *Ibid*, 78.

¹⁵⁴ *Ibid*, 81.

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid*.

7.12 Readmission Process and International Cooperation

Sweden entered into 15 bilateral readmission agreements with various countries, both within and outside the EU, starting with Germany in 1956 (see Table no. 6).¹⁵⁶ These countries include Iraq, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Estonia, France, Kosovo, Croatia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Switzerland, Germany, and Vietnam. Furthermore, from 2008 to 2022, Sweden has been a party to 18 EU and bilateral agreements, extending to countries such as Ukraine, Turkey, Sri Lanka, Serbia, Russia, Pakistan, Montenegro, Moldova, North Macedonia, Macao, Cape Verde, Hong Kong, Georgia, Bosnia, Belarus, Azerbaijan, Armenia, and Albania.

8. Funding (Budget) and Programmes Related to Return

According to information published on the Swedish Migration Agency's website, the available funding (budget) and financial support and programs related to the return process are as follows:

Table 2: Funding (Budget) and Programmes Related to Return

Link	Cash support for re-establishment	Other form of Support	Link
https://tinyurl.com/49bv44f2	Adult: 30000 SEK	Reception on arrival at the airport in your country of origin	https://tinyurl.com/y6wtyatt
	Child: 15000 SEK	Temporary accommodation in your country of origin	
	Family: 75000 SEK	Allowance for setting up your own business in your country of origin	
	Post-arrival Support for the three days: 615 EUR	Help with getting onto the job market in your country of origin	
		Education (including vocational training)	
		Job advice	
		Support in contact with the authorities in your country of origin	
		Legal advice	
		Medical care	

¹⁵⁶ Swedish Migration Agency, Planeringsavdelningen/Norrköping, Enheten för statistik och analys, email Correspondence with Philip Engman, statistician, in September and November 2023 (on file with the authors).

9. Gaps in the Return Regime and Policy Recommendations

9.1. Introductory Remarks

The concept of “gaps” may have several different meanings. It may, for example, refer to a gap in the implementation of laws and policies (an implementation gap), a gap between public discourse and policy on paper (a discursive gap) or the difference between the implemented policies and their effect on, for example, migration (an efficacy gap).¹⁵⁷ The consequences of the gaps may also be perceived as positive or negative depending on whom you ask: for the failed asylum seeker, an implementation gap between a restrictive return policy and its implementation in practice may be perceived as a positive thing as it may postpone or delay the enforcement of a deportation decision. In contrast, the same lack of implementation may be harmful from the point of view of the policymaker whose credibility relies on enforcing a restrictive return regime. In this section, we list various gaps in the legal, institutional and international cooperation frameworks in the Swedish return field, which we have identified during the research carried out for this report, as well as recommendations on how to bridge or counteract the gaps.

9.2. Legal Gaps

A. *Lack of definitions of the concepts identified in the Return Directive, Article 3 in particular*

The Swedish Aliens Act does not specifically include several of the definitions lined up in the Return Directive, Article 3, such as “irregular stay”, “return”, “removal”, “rejection, refusal, removal, expulsion or deportation decision”, “vulnerable individuals” or “assisted return”. In the 2011 government bill on the implementation of the Return Directive into Swedish law, the government held that introducing the definitions into the Aliens Act was not necessary as the existing legal framework (the Aliens Act and related legislation, for example, on the right to health care for asylum seekers) already aligned with the Directive’s requirements on this point. It may be noted that the Aliens Act indeed includes some definitions (see the Aliens Act, Chapter 1) but not a complete list of all the concepts used in the Act. In the case of the Return Directive, some definitions, or at least descriptions, indeed have been incorporated into the Aliens Act – Chapter 1, Section 15 on the risk of absconding being one example – but in general the meaning of the concepts is to be understood either indirectly (as in “illegal/irregular stay” being the opposite to “legal stay”), or through reading the grounds on which a decision on for example refusal-of-entry/rejection, or on expulsion may be taken. While there may be logic in not making an already comprehensive Aliens Act even heavier with definitions and instead referring to the definitions stated in the Return Directive itself, the lack of definitions may

¹⁵⁷ Malm Lindberg, “The Tricky Thing of Implementing Migration Policies: Insights from Return Policies in Sweden,” 157.

create legal uncertainty on which rules apply and their content. In other words, the more unclear the legal status is, the less stable it becomes, making access to rights precarious.

Recommendation 1: incorporate the definitions outlined in the Return Directive, Article 3, in the Aliens Act.

B. Unclearities regarding what constitutes “a practical impediment” to enforcing a return decision and when such an impediment should be taken into account

The Aliens Act, Chapter 8, Section 7 requires that in the assessment of whether a decision on refusal-of-entry or expulsion may be taken, the prevalence of impediments to enforcement as described in the Aliens Act Chapter 12, as well as other possible impediments to enforcement, must be taken into account (see also Chapter 8 Section 15 on EEA citizens and Chapter 8 a Section 3 on expulsion due to criminal activity). If such impediments exist, a residence permit typically should be granted. The impediments to enforcement may be related to the risk of non-refoulement (Aliens Act Chapter 12, Section 1-3 a), be of a practical nature (for example, that the person will not be allowed entry or cannot get travel documents), or of a medical nature. Chapter 12 Section 18 addresses the situation *after* a return decision has taken legal effect, when certain impediments to the enforcement of a decision on refusal of entry or expulsion may, even if they have occurred after the decision has taken legal effect, lead to a residence permit being granted. Such impediments include, following Chapter 12, Section 18, Subsection 2, *i*) the risk of non-refoulement, *ii*) when there is reason to assume that the receiving country will not allow the alien entry and *iii*) medical reasons and "other particular reasons". The second impediment mentioned here is referred to by the term practical impediments to enforcing a return decision. While not explicitly stated in the Aliens Act, the preparatory works underline that the difficulties in such a situation to implement the decision must, according to the government, not in any part be due to the individual's refusal to cooperate in the implementation.¹⁵⁸

It can be noted that although the term "practical impediments" is not included in the Aliens Act, it is nevertheless a well-established term used in preparatory works by the migration authorities and in case law. The gap identified here has several aspects: *i*) that the term as such is not included in the Aliens Act may lead to unclearities as to when the prevalence of such impediments must be taken into account, *ii*) the lack of definition of what constitutes a practical impediment to enforcement may cause uncertainty as to what constitutes such an impediment and *iii*) it is, as has been pointed out in a 2017 report of a Government Inquiry on practical impediments to enforcement, somewhat unclear what is required of the alien in order to be considered to have sufficiently participated in the implementation of the decision.

Recommendation 2: The Aliens Act should include a definition of what may constitute "a practical impediment" to enforcing a return decision.

We do not formulate any recommendation stating that what is required for an alien to be considered not having participated in or contributed to implementing the return decision should be specified in the Aliens Act. However, it would be helpful if the Migration Court of

¹⁵⁸ Prop. (Government Bill), *Ny instans- och processordning i utlännings- och medborgarskapsärenden* 2004/05:170, 299.

Appeal addressed the issue and clarified what expectations can be placed on the individual in these cases.

C. The provisions on detention in the Aliens Act do not sufficiently align with EU law

There are grounds on which a person can be held in detention in the Reception Directive (recast), the Asylum Procedures Directive (recast), the Return Directive and the Dublin Regulation (recast). The various grounds for detention differ in the different directives, and thus also for the various categories of TCNs. The conditions for detention in the context of return are specified in the Return Directive, Article 15. However, the rules on detention in the Aliens Act do not distinguish between different TCNs, and the rules in the Aliens Act, Chapter 10, Section 1 apply to all categories. The differences between the EU Directives and Swedish law may cause problems. For example, it is consistent with the wording in Chapter 10, Section 1, to detain an asylum seeker on the grounds of probability. However, as the Migration Court of Appeal has pointed out in MIG 2020:14 and 2021:3, such detention must comply with the Reception Directive Article 8.3 for it to be legal. While the Migration Court of Appeal in MIG 2020:2 made clear that the provisions on detention in the Aliens Act must be interpreted and implemented in line with EU law, it may be argued that the lack of specificity in the Aliens Act may lead to decisions on detention that do not have a solid legal ground in an EU law perspective. It is interesting to note that the Government Inquiry on detention established in August 2023 (dir. 2023:119) while being instructed to analyze the compatibility of Swedish law and EU law on detention, including detention for the purpose of enforcing a return decision, seems to focus mainly on exploring additional grounds for detention in EU law compared to Swedish law, and not specifically look into whether Swedish law needs adjusting in order to adhere to minimum standards as established by the Directives.

Recommendation 3: Further analysis is needed to establish whether Swedish law on detention is consistent with minimum standards established in EU law.

D. The rules pertaining to the refusal-of-entry or expulsion of an alien who has permission to reside in another EU state does not fully align with EU law

In April of 2023, the CJEU in the case C-629/22¹⁵⁹ (which concerned Sweden and the validity of the Aliens Act Chapter 8, Section 6 a, subsection 2), found that the Return Directive, Article 6.2, requires states to allow irregular aliens with the possibility to return to the member state in which they hold a residence permit to do so before the national authorities issue a decision on return. The CJEU concludes that

the Return Directive, Article 6(2) must be interpreted as meaning that the competent authorities of a Member State are required to permit a third-country national staying illegally on the territory of that Member State who holds a valid residence permit or other authorization offering a right to stay issued by another Member State to go to that other Member State before they adopt, if the circumstances so require, a return

¹⁵⁹ CJEU, C-629/22, ECLI:EU: C:2023:365.

decision in respect of such a national, even though those authorities consider it likely that that national will not comply with a request to go to that other Member State.¹⁶⁰

The CJEU moreover held that

an interpretation of Article 6(2) to the effect that that provision permits the competent authorities of the Member States to adopt a return decision where it is 'likely' that the third-country national concerned will not comply with a request to go immediately to the territory of the Member State which issued him or her with a valid residence permit or other authorization offering a right of residence would amount to establishing a derogation which is not provided for in Article 6(2) and would therefore deprive that provision of its practical effect.¹⁶¹

The CJEU case concerned Sweden and the implementation of the Aliens Act, Chapter 8 Section 6 a, subsections 1-2, which implements the Return Directive Article 6.2 but also allows for derogation from the duty to instruct an alien to leave the country and, also, from refraining from issuing a return decision if, for example, there are reasonable grounds to assume that such an instruction would not be adhered to (subsection 2, item 5). As pointed out by the CJEU, the Swedish provision seems to offer more leeway for the state to decide when to allow the alien to leave the country without being the subject of a return decision. This decision may have additional adverse effects for the individual if combined with an entry ban. The CJEU ruling so far, from what we have been able to establish, has yet to lead to any changes in the guidance provided by the Migration Agency or in case law, and certainly not on the legislative level.

Recommendation 4: The Migration Agency and the Police Authority should draft guidelines on the implementation of the Aliens Act, Chapter 8, Section 6 a, to ensure compliance with the CJEU case law.

9.3. Policy Gaps

E. Mixed messages – does “no” always mean “no”?

It is a clearly stated aim in Swedish migration policy that an individual present on Swedish territory without the necessary permits to be there is to leave the country, preferably voluntarily. “A no needs to mean no”, as the Minister of Migration Maria Malmer Stenergard repeatedly has stated, for the system to function or to remain credible and predictable (both essential in a legal certainty perspective).¹⁶² At the same time, the nature of migration law, asylum law in particular, which in essence concerns assessing future risk, means that a “no” needs to take into account the fact that new circumstances might arise that presents obstacles towards enforcing a return decision (new information about persecution, for example), or prevent such a decision from being taken in the first place (such as humanitarian grounds, or family ties).

¹⁶⁰ Ibid, 27.

¹⁶¹ Ibid, 26.

¹⁶² Cf. Moderaterna (the Conservative Party) <https://moderaterna.se/nyhet/atta-forslag-att-fler-ska-utvisas-ett-nej-ska-vara-ett-nej/> (last accessed January 4, 2024) and Swedish Radio (Sveriges Radio), <https://sverigesradio.se/artikel/regeringen-infor-atervandandecenter-vill-oka-atervandringen> (last accessed January 4, 2024).

In later years, Swedish migration policy has been criticized for sending “mixed messages” to asylum seekers. The critique refers to the state, on the one hand emphasizing that “no means no” and allocating resources to increase the number of returns, and on the other hand allowing for asylum seekers to “change track” from asylum to work permits, for practical impediments to enforcement of return decisions (such as the receiving state not issuing travel documents) to generate temporary residence permits (thus prolonging the stay in Sweden), and for return decisions not to be enforced before the limitation period is over, allowing for a new application to be submitted and the process to start anew, to mention just a few examples.¹⁶³ The point made by critics is that this creates uncertainty as well as false hopes, and may lead to the system not functioning the way it is intended, thus losing legitimacy, as well as unnecessary suffering among failed asylum seekers and other migrants. While the present Government and its support party strongly emphasize the “no means no-approach”, examples including proposals on abolishing both the “track change-option” and limitation times¹⁶⁴, there is a danger that a single-minded focus on restrictive measures might increase the risk for fundamental rights such as protection from persecution and the right to family life to be overridden.

Recommendation 5: The Government should ensure that, while seeking to fulfil the goal “no means no,” fundamental rights are safeguarded and that return-related legislation includes safety-valve clauses.

F. Compliance of many of the proposed reforms in the 2022 Tidö Agreement with the fundamental human rights of migrants

The 2022 Tidö Agreement between the Conservative/Liberal Government and its populist right-wing support party, the Sweden Democrats, contains a considerable amount of proposals for reforms of Swedish migration policy. The reforms, including those on the matter of return, have a common denominator – the aim to make Swedish migration policy more restrictive and to make Sweden less attractive to asylum seekers and other categories of migrants – migration policy as a deterrence measure. Return-related proposals include (but are not limited to) abolishing or considerably prolonging limitation periods for the validity of return decisions, prolonging the validity of an entry ban, increasing focus on finding people staying irregularly in Sweden and providing the Police Authority with an increased mandate to do so, increase the number of places in detention centres, discharging the possibility for people having been granted asylum to be granted a permanent residence permit, increased focus on the cessation of residence permits, severely increase the number of people opting for “voluntary repatriation”, use development aid as a tool to increase returns and counteract irregular migration and deny people staying irregularly in Sweden any access to financial support from municipalities. The human rights perspective and the perspective of the migrant are all but absent from the reform agenda, which, among many other concerns, raises doubt as to the proposal’s compatibility with Sweden’s human rights obligations and the Swedish Constitution. A majority of the proposals are now being analyzed by government inquiries or

¹⁶³ This was one of the points raised by the expert panel in the GAPs Work Package 2 roundtable on Swedish return policy, held 20 December 2023.

¹⁶⁴ Dir. 2023:126, Tilläggsdirektiv till utredningen om stärkt återvändandeverksamhet (Ju 2022:12).

prepared by the Ministry of Justice, and the aim is for as many as possible to be implemented before the September 2026 general elections.

Recommendation 6: We urge the Government to keep in mind that even a restrictive migration policy must take into account and respect the fundamental human rights also of irregular migrants present on the territory and that Sweden's binding legal obligations in the field of human rights and refugee law are minimum standards that must be adhered to. We also urge the Government to consider the proportionality of the reforms outlined in the Tidö Agreement and their effects on the integration of migrants into Swedish society.

G. Internal immigration control and the risk of racial profiling

One of the measures suggested in the Tidö Agreement in the context of return is an increased focus on identifying and finding people staying irregularly in Sweden. One of the measures suggested to achieve this goal is an extended mandate for the Police Authority regarding internal immigration control. Historically, an increased focus on random identity checks, for example, on public transport (the REVA project of the early 2010s), has raised questions about racial profiling and targeting of individuals of a particular category. While such profiling is prohibited, concerns may be raised as to whether such practices may resurface in light of the pressure put on the Police Authority to intensify the identification of irregular migrants in Sweden.

Recommendation 7: For the Police Authority to make it a top priority racial profiling does not take place when conducting internal immigration control, and for the Government, when extending the Police Authority's mandate in this respect, to be explicit that racial profiling must be avoided at all costs.

H. Sudden changes in conditions for residence permits

Recently, several of the grounds on which a person may be eligible for a residence permit have been questioned, and some have also changed. Many of these changes have entered into force without there being any provisional regulations, meaning that conditions may change from one day to another and that a person during, for example, the asylum process or the process of prolonging a residence permit based on employment, no longer is eligible for said permit. One example is the humanitarian ground "particularly distressing circumstances" in the Aliens Act Chapter 5, Section 6, subsection 2, which was abolished and ceased to apply on 1 December 2023. The remaining humanitarian ground, "severely distressing circumstances", raises the bar. Fewer individuals will likely be able to be granted a residence permit on this basis.

A second example is the minimum salary required for a person to be granted a work-based residence permit in Sweden, which, as of 1 November 2023, was increased from 13,000 SEK to 27,360 SEK. The new rules do not apply to individuals who already have a permit but will affect them once their work permit needs prolongation. It also applies to individuals who had submitted their applications but had yet to receive a decision when the change entered into force. The substantial raise in the minimum wage is intended to ensure that aliens working in Sweden may support themselves, but it has been criticized for being unnecessarily high, thus risking that people working in, for example, the service sector will not be able to meet these

conditions when their current permit expires and end up either returning to their countries of origin, leaving Swedish businesses, the health care sector and other sectors without the necessary workforce, or remaining in Sweden as irregular migrants. The lack of provisional measures sharpens the blow.

Recommendation 8: Provisional measures must be included when introducing stricter measures limiting the possibility of being granted a residence permit. Moreover, the proportionality and long-term effects of the proposed measures must be properly evaluated. Restrictive rules cannot be a means in itself.

9.4. Institutional gaps

I. The lack of updated, easily accessible statistical data on returns

One of the main obstacles when drafting this report was collecting reliable data on the number of enforced return decisions, voluntary returns and forced returns. While the Migration Agency is the government authority responsible for data collection on migration-related matters, including return, data is not easily accessible or presented in a systematic and disaggregated way, making external evaluation of return policies and practices complicated, contributing to unclarity to prevail and the dissemination of disinformation.

Recommendation 7: The Government should instruct the Migration Agency to present accurate, updated, disaggregated, and easily accessible statistical data on return on its website.

J. Implementing the legal framework in practice

The legal framework for return, of which we have tried to provide an overview in this report, in theory, is relatively well-functioning: there are procedural guarantees, the right to appeal both a denial of a residence permit (and the return decision accompanying it) and detention decisions, general clauses are emphasizing the principle of proportionality (cf. the Aliens Act Chapter 1, Section 8) and the child rights perspective to mention a few examples. At the same time, there have over the years been numerous accounts and reports of people being held in immigration detention on a long-term basis without clear legal grounds, on the difficult situation in many detention centres, not least for young people, on attempts to execute return decisions to countries to which the person to be returned has very weak, if any, ties, and on the child-rights perspective often having to step back in favour of upholding a restrictive migration policy. This is a cause for concern, perhaps even more so in the current climate in Swedish migration policy and the paradigm shift towards a more restrictive position.

Recommendation 9: Echoing previous recommendations on legal certainty, respect for fundamental human rights, and proportionality, we call upon those tasked with implementing the legislation, irrespective of its restrictiveness, to safeguard respect for human rights, human dignity, and to refrain from equating irregularity with illegality.

10 Appendices

Table 3: Conventions within the framework of the Council of Europe that Sweden has ratified ¹⁶⁵

Name of the treaty	Time of signing	Time of ratification
Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ETS No. 005)	28/11/1950	04/02/1952
Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ETS No. 009)	20/03/1952	22/06/1953
European Social Charter (ETS No. 035)	18/10/1961	17/12/1962
Protocol No. 4 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, securing certain rights and freedoms other than those already included in the Convention and in the first Protocol thereto (ETS No. 046)	16/09/1963	13/06/1964
Protocol No. 6 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms concerning the Abolition of the Death Penalty (ETS No. 114)	28/04/1983	09/02/1984
Protocol No. 7 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ETS No. 117)	22/11/1984	08/11/1985
European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (ETS No. 126)	26/11/1987	21/06/1988
Additional Protocol to the European Social Charter (ETS No. 128)	05/05/1988	05/05/1989
Additional Protocol to the European Social Charter Providing for a System of Collective Complaints (ETS No. 158)	09/11/1995	01/07/1998
European Social Charter (revised) (ETS No. 163)	03/05/1996	29/05/1998
Protocol No. 12 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ETS No. 177)	04/11/2000	01/04/2005

¹⁶⁵ Please see for more information the Council of Europe's website <https://shorturl.at/aceqE>

Source: Council of Europe

Table 4. Ratification Status for Sweden of International Human Rights Treaties and Refugee Law Instruments¹⁶⁶

Treaty Names	Treaty Name Abbreviation	Signature date	Ratification date, Accession (a), Succession (b) date
Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees		28 July 1951	26 October 1954
Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees			4 October 1967
Convention against Torture and Other Cruel Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment	CAT	4 February 1985	8 January 1986
Optional Protocol of the Convention against Torture	CAT-OP	26 June 2003	14 September 2005
International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights	CCPR	29 September 1967	6 December 1971
Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights aiming to the abolition of the death penalty	CCPR-OP2-DP	13 February 1990	11 May 1990
Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance	CED	6 February 2007	
Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women	CEDAW	7 March 1980	2 July 1980
International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination	CERD	5 May 1966	6 December 1971
International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights	CESCR	29 September 1967	6 December 1971

¹⁶⁶ For more information see the United Nations, United Nations Treaty Database, https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/15/TreatyBodyExternal/Treaty.aspx?CountryID=168&Lang=EN (accessed 18 March 2024).

Convention on the Rights of the Child	CRC	26 January 1990	29 June 1990
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict	CRC-OP-AC	8 June 2000	20 February 2003
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children child prostitution and child pornography	CRC-OP-SC	8 September 2000	19 January 2007
Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities	CRPD	30 March 2007	15 December 2008

Source: UN Treaty body database

Table 5. Acceptance of Individual Complaints Procedures for Sweden¹⁶⁷

Treaty Names	Treaty Name Abbreviation	Acceptance of Individual Complaints procedures	Date of Acceptance/ non-acceptance
Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights	CCPR-OP1	Yes	06 Dec 1971
Individual complaints procedure under the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination	CERD, Art.14	Yes	06 Dec 1971
Individual complaints procedure under the Convention against Torture	CAT, Art.22	Yes	08 Jan 1986
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women	CEDAW-OP	Yes	24 Apr 2003
Optional protocol to the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities	CRPD-OP	Yes	15 Dec 2008

Source: UN Treaty Body Database

¹⁶⁷ Ibid.

Table 6: EU and Bilateral Readmission Agreements

Countries	EU and Bilateral readmission agreements	Entered into force	"EU source/Swedish Official Gazette."	Link
Albania	EU	2006-05-01	2005/371/EG EUT L 124/22	På engelska
Armenia	EU	2014-01-01	2013/629/EU EUT L 289/13	På engelska
Azerbaijan	EU	2014-09-01	2014/239/EU EUT L 128/17	På engelska
Belarus	EU	2020-07-01	2020/751/EU EUT L 181/3	På engelska
Bosnia	EU	2008-01-01	2007/820/EG EUT L 334/66	På engelska
Georgia	EU	2011-03-01	2011/118/EU EUT L 52/47	På engelska
Hong Kong	EU	2004-06-01	2004/80/EG EUT L 17/25	På engelska
Cape Verde	EU	2014-12-01	2013/522/EU EUT L 282/15	På engelska
Macao	EU	2004-06-01	2004/424/EG EUT L 143/99	På engelska
Macedonia	EU	2008-01-01	2007/817/EG EUT L 334/7	På engelska
Moldavia	EU	2008-01-01	2007/826/EG EUT L 334/149	På engelska
Montenegro	EU	2008-01-01	2007/818/EG EUT L 334/26	På engelska
Pakistan	EU	2010-10-07	2010/649/EU EUT L 287/52	På engelska
Russia	EU	2007-06-01	2007/341/EG EUT L 129/40	På engelska
Serbia	EU	2008-01-01	2007/819/EG EUT L 334/46	På engelska
Sri Lanka	EU	2005-05-01	2005/372/EG EUT L 124/43	På engelska
Turkey	EU	2014-05-07	2014/252/EU EUT L 134/3	På engelska
Ukraine	EU	2008-01-01	2007/849/EG EUT L 332/48	På engelska
Iraq	Bilateral	2008-02-18	SÖ 2008:10	
Bulgaria	Bilateral	2005-08-01	SÖ 1999:6	
Cyprus	Bilateral	2006-02-17	SÖ 2006:26	
Estonia	Bilateral	1997-05-02	SÖ 1997:27	
France	Bilateral	1991-06-29	SÖ 1991:16	
Kosovo	Bilateral	2012-01-01	SÖ 2012:3	
Croatia	Bilateral	2003-04-06	SÖ 2003:6	
Latvia	Bilateral	1997-05-01	SÖ 1997:10	
Lithuania	Bilateral	1997-05-24	SÖ 1997:1	
Poland	Bilateral	1999-04-09	SÖ 1999:2	

Romania	Bilateral	2002-02-10	SÖ 2002:5	
Switzerland	Bilateral	2003-01-09	SÖ 2003:48	
Slovakia	Bilateral	2005-04-05	SÖ 2005:2	
Germany	Bilateral	1954-06-01	SÖ 1954:80	
Vietnam	Bilateral	2008-12-31	SÖ 2008:36	

Source: The Migration Agency

Table 7: Legislative Framework of Return Regime in Sweden

The Title of the Policy/Legislation in English	The Title in the Original Language	Policy Type/Area	Date/Announced Year	Level of Legislation	Type of Legislation or Administrative Action	Department or Agencies or National Law Enforcement mentioned in the Policy/Legislation (Optional)
The Aliens Act (SFS 2005:716)	Utlänningslag (SFS 2005:716)	assisted return, border management, forced return, general/asylum, pre-removal detention, other	2005 (entry into force 2006)	National	Act	Migration Agency, Migration Courts, Migration Court of Appeal, Police Authority
The Aliens Ordinance (SFS 2006:97)	Utlänningsförordning (SFS 2006:97)	general/asylum, forced return, border management	2006	National	Decree	Migration Agency, Migration Courts, Migration Court of Appeal

Act (2022:700) on special control of certain foreigners	Lag (2022:700) om särskild kontroll av vissa utlänningar	other, pre-removal detention	2022	National	Act	Security Police, Migration Agency, Migration Court of Appeal, the Government
The Act on residence permits for students at upper secondary level (2017:353)	Lag (2017:353) om uppehållstillstånd för studerande på gymnasial nivå	general/asylum, other	2017	National	Act	Migration Agency, Migration Courts, Migration Court of Appeal
the Administrative Procedure Act (2017:900).	Förvaltningslag (2017:900)	general/asylum, other, forced return, assisted return	2017	National	Act	Migration Courts, Migration Courts of Appeal
The temporary Act (2016:752) on temporary restrictions on the possibility of obtaining residence permits in Sweden."	den tillfälliga lagen (Lag (2016:752) om tillfälliga begränsningar av möjligheten att få uppehållstillstånd i Sverige	general/asylum, assisted return, forced return, other, irregularity, pre-removal detention	2016-2021 July	National	Act	Migration Agency, Migration Courts, Migration Court of Appeal
The Unaccompanied Minors Guardian Act (2005:429)	Lag (2005:429) om god man för ensamkommande barn	general/asylum	2005	National	Act	Migration Agency, Migration Courts, Migration

						Court of Appeal
Reception of Asylum Seekers Act (LMA) (1994:137)	Lag (1994:137) om mottagande av asylsökande m.fl. (LMA)	general/asylum, other	1994	National	Act	Migration Agency
Ordinance on Reception of Asylum Seekers and others (1994:361)	Förordning (1994:361) om mottagande av asylsökande m.fl.	general/asylum, pre-removal detention, other	1994	National	Decree	Migration Agency
Act on health care for asylum seekers and others. (2008:344)	Lag (2008:344) om hälso- och sjukvård åt asylsökande m.fl.	general/asylum, pre-removal detention, forced return	2008	National	Act	Migration Agency
Ordinance on health care for asylum seekers etc. (2008:347)	Förordning (2008:347) om hälso- och sjukvård åt asylsökande m.fl.	general/asylum, other	2008	National	Decree	Migration Agency
Ordinance on state compensation for healthcare for asylum seekers. (1996:1357)	Förordning (1996:1357) om statlig ersättning för hälso- och sjukvård till asylsökande	general/asylum	1997	National	Decree	Migration Agency
Ordinance on re-establishment support for certain	Förordning (2008:778) om återetableringssstöd för vissa utlänningar	assisted return, other	2008	National	Decree	Migration Agency

foreigners (2008:778)						
Act (2021:1187) with supplementary provisions to the EU's regulations on the Schengen Information System.	Lag (2021:1187) med kompletterande bestämmelser till EU:s förfordningar om Schengens informationssystem	other	2021 (entry into force 2023)		Act	Migration Agency
The Detention Act (2010:611)	Häkteslag (2010:611)	forced return, irregularity , assisted return	2010	National	Act	Police Authority
the Act of judicial procedure (RB 1942:740)	Rättegångsbalk (1942:740)	forced return	1942	National	Act	Migration Courts, Migration Courts of Appeal
Act (2018:1693) on the police's processing of personal data within the scope of the Criminal Data Act	Lag (2018:1693) om polisens behandling av personuppgifter inom brottsdatalogens område	forced return	2018	National	Act	Police Authority

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